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Authors	Albert Meroño-Peñuela (KCL), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Fiorela Ciroku (UNIBO), Valentina Carriero (UNIBO), Mari Wigham (NISV), Enrico Daga (OU), Eleonora Marzi (UNIBO), Elena Musumeci (MiC), Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW), Andrea Scharnhorst (KNAW), James McDermott (NUI), Philippe Rigaux (CNAM), Christophe Guillotel-Nothmann (CNRS), Simon Holland (OU)

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Project Contacts

Project Coordinator

Valentina Presutti

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM -
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Department of Language,
Literature and Modern Cultures
(LILEC)

E-mail:

valentina.presutti@unibo.it

Project Manager

Marta Clementi

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM -
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Research division

E-mail: marta.clementi3@unibo.it

POLIFONIA Consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA	Italy
2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

One of the key missions of the Polifonia project is to build and interlink knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage. These interconnected music knowledge graphs act as a *data backbone* for the project. This deliverable is centred around one of the ten Polifonia pilots: INTERLINK. The INTERLINK pilot is not bound to a specific institutional dataset, collection or use case; but rather summarises the common needs of all pilots of representing their data as music knowledge graphs, and finding meaningful connections among them.

Existing work in the relevant areas of knowledge engineering, knowledge graph construction, and knowledge graph interlinking is promising but presents a number of pitfalls in its direct application to Polifonia from the point of view of achieving this knowledge graph building and interlinking: (a) existing knowledge engineering methodologies do not account for “in-between” knowledge graph construction processes that are not fully distributed nor local; (b) in an integrated vision of European musical cultural heritage through knowledge graphs, both musical content and its ‘context’ or metadata need to co-exist; and (c) no current techniques address the issue of finding missing links between different music knowledge graphs at scale, accounting for this co-existence of musical content and context in the same knowledge graph.

This deliverable describes our efforts, particularly gathered in Polifonia’s WP2 and Task T2.3, in addressing these challenges, delivering: (a) a scalable methodology for knowledge graph construction that is well suited for the project and sits in-between the two classic extremes of ontology engineering; (b) a music knowledge graph construction framework that leverages modules of the Polifonia Ontology Network and the SPARQL Anything tool; and (c) a music knowledge graph interlinking framework, based on both heuristics and neural network-based link prediction through music knowledge graph embeddings.

The latter two are evaluated in two different use-cases, the **ChoCo-KG** chord annotation knowledge graph, and the **MIDI2vec** music knowledge graph interlinking method, with encouraging results.

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1 Introduction

One of the key missions of the Polifonia project is to build and interlink knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage. These interconnected music knowledge graphs act as a *data backbone* for the project, not just as a form of a dynamic and schema-free database that can be easily used in pilots, demonstrations, prototypes, or the Web Portal; but also as a proper contribution and project output for other stakeholders to repurpose and reuse. Knowledge graphs, which are graphs “of data intended to accumulate and convey knowledge of the real world, whose nodes represent entities of interest and whose edges represent relations between these entities”, have been successfully deployed for solving problems of data interoperability and integration in various domains [1] (e.g. Web search, healthcare, science, etc.), and in Polifonia we develop them further to also address these issues in the interesting, albeit disconnected and often siloed, data collections that hold our European musical cultural heritage. Knowledge graphs have the potential, therefore, to be the technical archetype to help us discover their hidden connections and relationships.

In various ways, this deliverable is centred around one of the ten Polifonia pilots: INTERLINK. The INTERLINK pilot is a bit different from the rest of Polifonia pilots, as it is not bound to a specific institutional dataset, collection or use case; but rather summarises the common needs of all pilots of representing their data as music knowledge graphs, and finding meaningful connections among them. For these reasons, INTERLINK is discussed more prominently and, as we will see, provides the general framework for the construction and interlinking of music knowledge graphs in Polifonia. This deliverable has, therefore, obvious connections to content presented elsewhere in deliverables D1.1 [2] describing the socio-technical roadmap; D2.1 [3] describing the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON); and D2.7 [4] presenting the project’s knowledge graph testing infrastructure.

Building and interlinking knowledge graphs¹ about music is not new, and has been attempted before in different ways. Prominent results are MusicBrainz [5] and the Music Ontology [6], which have been used to represent and annotate large databases of musical metadata (composers, bands, songs, albums, releases, etc.); and have been extended various times. But beyond music metadata, some of the hidden connections in European cultural heritage may lie in the music content itself (notes, chords, scales, modes, tones, keys, etc.) or its context (historical events, annotations) and patterns. Here, literature is more scarce. The Music Theory ontology [7], the

¹We use the phrase *building and interlinking knowledge graphs* in a broad sense, covering two key activities: (i) the *conversion* of original datasets to a knowledge graph representation language (RDF) and an established set of vocabulary resources, classes and properties (the Polifonia Ontology Network, PON); and (ii) the *enrichment* of such conversion by establishing new links that otherwise would have not been available through the mere conversion in the previous step. Typically we use *building* to refer to the former and *interlinking* to refer to the latter; but in what follows “building” knowledge graphs has to be interpreted as the process of both data conversion, representation and enrichment.

Music Score ontology [8] and the Music Notation ontology [9] are helpful in representing music notation and scores, and the Chord ontology [10] can do so with chords. However, these ontologies are scarcely used for the construction of large musical knowledge graphs. Perhaps the only exception is the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [11], a large music knowledge graph of 10B+ RDF triples of interconnected symbolic music information from 500K+ MIDI files from the Web [12]. An important methodological aspect revolves around what work methodology is adequate for the construction and interlinking of these music knowledge graphs in Polifonia. Various collaborative ontology engineering methodologies exist, such as DILIGENT [13], NeOn [14], eXtreme Design [15] or that which emerges from Wikidata [16]. Finally, the specific issue of building and interlinking knowledge graphs has been addressed for both structured and, more recently, unstructured (natural language) data sources. Knowledge graphs from structured data sources can be constructed with RML [17] (which covers XML, TSV, JSON, APIs, etc.), OpenRefine [18], TabLinker [19], SPARQL Anything [20], and a large et cetera. Unstructured (natural language) sources can be used for building knowledge graphs too [21], and have been used in medicine [22], scientific papers [23], and common sense knowledge bases [24].

All these areas are relevant for the goal of building and interlinking music knowledge graphs, but fall short in the following aspects:

- **Collaborative knowledge engineering methodologies.** Existing methodologies do not account for “in-between” knowledge graph construction processes that are not as distributed as in e.g. Wikidata (tens of thousands of contributors), and not as local and small-dataset based as in classic ontology engineering methodologies. Polifonia, with its ten pilots, sits in-between these two extremes of the spectrum. Most collaborative ontology engineering methodologies emphasize the ontology development process, but do not directly address the *knowledge graph engineering process* [1], which incorporates various other tasks and activities.
- **Musical content and context knowledge graphs.** In an integrated vision of European musical cultural heritage through knowledge graphs, both musical content (i.e. the music itself, as in [11]) and its ‘context’ or metadata (i.e. as covered by [6]) need to co-exist within the same data representation. For example: how can we publish integrated, machine-readable, large scale chord annotation datasets as knowledge graphs from disparate collections?
- **Techniques for interlinking music knowledge graphs at scale.** No current techniques address the issue of finding missing links between different music knowledge graphs at scale, accounting for this co-existence of musical content and context in the same knowledge graph. For example: a large number of MIDI files from the Web are missing relevant metadata, such as composer name or genre. How can we find those missing links in MIDI (and other kinds of symbolic-based) music representations?

This deliverable describes our efforts, particularly gathered in Polifonia’s WP2 and Task T2.3, in addressing these challenges. The contributions of this deliverable are:

- A scalable methodology for knowledge graph construction that is well suited for the project and sits in-between the two classic extremes of ontology engineering. To illustrate it, we describe the outcomes of the *Polifonia Knowledge Graph Pilot Clinics*, an effort to gather

requirements and offer technical solutions around the needs for knowledge graph construction and interlinking of the project's pilots

- A music knowledge graph construction framework, based on Musilar (content) and Cornucopia (context), the Similarity module of the Polifonia Ontology Network, and the SPARQL Anything tool [20]
- A music knowledge graph interlinking framework, based on both heuristics and neural network-based link prediction through music knowledge graph embeddings [25]

The latter two are evaluated in two different use-cases, the **ChoCo-KG** chord annotation knowledge graph, and the **MIDI2vec** music knowledge graph interlinking method, with encouraging results. ChoCo-KG is a knowledge graph based on the ChoCo (Chord Corpus) dataset², containing 30M+ RDF triples and 3K+ links to external datasets, which we have generated using the music knowledge graph construction framework that we propose. MIDI2vec [25] is a music knowledge graph embedding method that works on MIDI music represented as Polifonia music knowledge graphs [11].³ MIDI2vec can reliably learn models of symbolic music that relate entities in the graph to external entities, e.g. resources in other music knowledge graphs. We report the results on an experiment that uses a subset of the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [11] and discovers links to missing contextual information.

²A forthcoming publication will report on the details of the creation of the ChoCo dataset

³MIDI2vec has been developed between Polifonia researchers and collaborators in other institutions, and its first results have been recently published; see [25]

2 Related Work

The construction and linking of music cultural heritage knowledge graphs concerns related work in collaborative knowledge engineering –because Polifonia is a large, distributed consortium that needs to build such graphs in a collaborative manner–, musical data and music knowledge graphs –because we need a reference on what musical data is available, and what knowledge graphs have already been built with it–, knowledge graph construction –since KGs are the main artifact to be built–, and knowledge graph interlinking –since building the KGs does not necessarily produce links interconnecting them, a desirable feature when knowledge graphs exist in a distributed environment.

2.1 Collaborative Knowledge Engineering

Various knowledge engineering methodologies have been proposed over the years, primarily addressing the issue of how to engineer knowledge (mainly in the form of ontologies, but also considering knowledge graphs) at scale when a large number of knowledge workers participate in their construction. This gives rise to a whole new set of knowledge engineering activities that scarcely happen in small-scale knowledge graph construction, such as the definition of key roles, version control, flexibility towards the conceptualisation process, and tools for discussion and documentation. For a comprehensive survey on collaborative ontology engineering, see [26]. This section provides a high-level summary of a few of the most important collaborative knowledge engineering methodologies.

DILIGENT. This ontology engineering methodology [27] comprises the following main activities, which can involve both domain experts, users, knowledge and ontology engineers: building an initial ontology; local adaptation by the users; analysis and revision of the changes and feedback collected from the users; local update once a new version of the ontology is officially released. This methodology takes into account collaborative aspects and the involvement of different stakeholders. However, it does not provide any guidelines for the design of the ontology, and is not test-oriented. The first step, which consists in building an initial ontology, involves both domain experts, users, knowledge engineers and ontology engineers. The ontology can be then modified based on the feedback of the ontology users, which can locally adapt it (step 2) for their own purposes, and this feedback is collected by a *control board*, which decides how the ontology should be changed (step 3 and 4). Once a new version of the ontology is released, the users update their own local ontologies (step 5).

NeOn. The NeOn ontology engineering methodology does not prescribe a rigid workflow, but instead it suggests a variety of pathways for developing ontologies [14]. To do this, it proposes nine scenarios and further guidelines for each of them for building ontology networks and general

knowledge resources. These scenarios stem from all possible combinations between implementing ontologies from specifications from scratch without reuse, and reusing (or not), re-engineering (or taking as they are), merging (or keeping separate), restructuring, and localizing existing ontological and non-ontological resources and ontology design patterns. On the basis of this, NeOn proposes two ontology network life cycle models.

eXtreme Design. This agile ontology engineering methodology [15, 28] focuses on, and provides guidelines for, the reuse of ontology design patterns (ODPs), i.e. small reusable modelling solutions to recurrent modelling problems. It is iterative and incremental, involves different actors and teams, and is strongly test-based.

Wikidata. Wikidata is not a collaborative knowledge engineering methodology, but rather the world's largest open-source collaborative knowledge graph (KG) [16]. The reason we include Wikidata here is that it constitutes the prime example on how to build large knowledge graphs collaboratively when the number of contributors is arbitrarily unbound, and these contributors do not necessarily have ontology or knowledge graph expertise. Recent studies on Wikidata have looked into various sociotechnical concerns within the Wikidata community [29, 30, 31, 32, 33], and in particular in how it gets coordinated and organised when tasked with organising the knowledge of the world. It is, therefore, relevant to consider, especially in the context of Polifonia where experts in the music domain are as numerous, and perhaps outnumber, the number of ontology experts. This can provide critical clues as to what parts of a fully decentralised collaboration environment such as Wikidata can be reused and adapted in the context of building the Polifonia knowledge graph.

2.2 Music Ontologies, Datasets, and Knowledge Graphs

Existing music ontologies, datasets and knowledge graphs relevant for Polifonia and for knowledge graph construction and interlinking are thoroughly surveyed in D2.1 [3]. We summarise here the most important outcomes of that survey for completeness.

Various ontologies for diverse music-related applications exist, dealing with symbolic notation and audio signals at different levels of specificity. Some have been engineered for describing high-level music-related information, such as the The Music Ontology [6] – further extended with other modules such as the Audio Effects Ontology (AUFX-O) [34] and the Audio Features Ontology [35] –, the DOREMUS Ontology [36], the Performed Music Ontology (PMO) [37], and CoMus [38]. One application of Semantic Technologies to the musical field is the ETree project [39], which consists on a linked data set exposing meta-data from the Internet Archive Live Music Archive, containing over 17,000,000 triples describing 100,000 performances by 4,000 artists. Other ontologies describe musical notation: for example, the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [40] includes a MIDI ontology for representing symbolic music descriptions encoded in MIDI format, and the CHARM ontology [41] aims to describe musical structures based on the CHARM specifications. The Music Theory Ontology (MTO) [7] aims to describe theoretical concepts related to a music composition, while The Music Score Ontology (Music OWL) [8] represents similar concepts with a focus on music sheet notation. Finally, the Music Notation Ontology [9] focuses on the core

“semantic” information present in a score. Other ontologies aim to describe specific aspects of the musical domain, such as the Chord Ontology, the Tonality Ontology, the Temperament Ontology [10], and the Segment Ontology [42]. Other works describe audio signals or the procedures used to produce them, like The Audio Features Ontology [43], The Studio Ontology [44], and The Audio Effects Ontology [45]. Similarly, the Computational Analysis of the Live Music Archive (CALMA) [46] project aims to link metadata of music tracks with computational analyses of these recordings through feature extraction, clustering and classification. Additionally, ontologies have been used to model listeners’ habits and music tastes, as well as similarities between different musical pieces. The COMUS Ontology aims to represent users’ musical preferences and context [47]. Similarly, other ontologies were developed for music recommendation systems, as the Uniemotion: the Emotion Ontology [48] and the Similarity Ontology [49]. Finally, the Mobile audio ontology is a semantic audio framework for the design of novel music consumption experiences on mobile devices [50].

A large amount of music data, sometimes in the form of knowledge graphs, has been published in datasets such as LinkedBrainz¹ WASABI [51] that includes not only metadata but also audio analysis results. Other works focus instead on the music content itself, rather than on the music metadata. Other works are instead focused on the music content itself [52, 53]. Those ontologies have not been selected because of some unnecessary complexity of the representation, based on the structure and on the elements the score (parts, measures, etc.). The only experience of representation of MIDI in a graph has been realised in the *MIDI Linked Data Cloud* [11]; the used data model represents faithfully the sequence of MIDI events. However, this representation strategy is unable to directly capture some relevant music features, such as the note duration. To the best of our knowledge, the MIDI Linked Data Cloud is the largest music knowledge graph focusing on the representation of musical (symbolic) content. [3] includes a broad survey of datasets typically used in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and in the Polifonia pilots.

2.3 Knowledge Graph Construction

Various methodologies for building knowledge graphs have been recently proposed, primarily in two contexts: building knowledge graphs from unstructured data (i.e. texts in natural language), and building them from structured data such as CSV or JSON files, or relational databases. Both apply to Polifonia since pilot musical heritage data is rich in both types. A comprehensive survey can be found at [1].

Knowledge graph construction from text has recently attracted the attention of many NLP researchers [21], proposing various neural architectures for end-to-end KG construction, as well as task specific. For example, in the medical domain [22] propose a workflow of 8 steps (data preparation, entity recognition, entity normalization, relation extraction, property calculation, graph cleaning, related-entity ranking, and graph embedding) to generate knowledge graphs from electronic medical records (EMR). Similarly, in the task of constructing scientific knowledge graphs

¹<http://linkedbrainz.org/>

from scholarly papers, [23] propose a multi-task setup of identifying and classifying entities, relations, and coreference clusters in scientific articles, establishing thus these as the canonical entities to be represented in scientific knowledge graphs. Contrarily to these, commonsense knowledge bases have a less restrictive representation space, and transformer architectures have been successfully used for commonsense, open-text knowledge graph construction in e.g. COMET [24].

More traditionally, a variety of methods have been proposed, mostly in the context of the Semantic Web, for building knowledge graphs from structured sources. Inspired in work to map relational database schema and data to RDF knowledge graphs [54], RML proposes a general language to map a variety of structured languages (e.g. XML, TSV, JSON, APIs, etc.) into RDF knowledge graphs [17]. There are, however, various other tools that convert tabular data to RDF². CSV and HTML tables can be turned into RDF knowledge graphs too with dedicated tools [55, 56]. Larger frameworks, like the combination of Open Refine and DERI’s RDF plugin [57, 18], Opencube [58] and Grafter³ cover even more tabular and structured data formats, like Excel, JSON, XML, RDF, and Google Data documents, with varying levels of expressiveness as table layout can partly encode data semantics. For data sorted in these tables in an “eccentric” layout, typically with spanning and hierarchical headers, multidimensional views and arbitrary data locations [59, 60], tools like TabLinker [61] might be better suited. Custom code is also often used for dataset conversion when formats or models are too specific; Python’s `rdflib` is a good example.⁴ For a summary of other structured methods, especially suited for legacy data and historical datasets in the cultural heritage domain, see [62, 60].

Given the large variety of formats, schemas and representations present in European musical cultural heritage [3], the general method that seems best suited for Polifonia is SPARQL Anything [20]. This approach uses a unique data schema called Facade-X, a simple meta-model that allows converters to produce RDF from diverse data sources without the need of a domain vocabulary. As a result, the provision of such converters and data models specified in RDF allows users to write and execute SPARQL queries directly over the original data sources, without any intermediate conversion; effectively allowing to “SPARQL anything”. To do this in an interoperable way, i.e. without breaking compatibility to SPARQL standards [63], SPARQL Anything relies on overloading the `SERVICE` keyword as similarly done in e.g. SPARQL service-oriented approaches [64, 65]. In combination with the `CONSTRUCT` SPARQL operator, RDF knowledge graphs can effectively be constructed directly on top of source datasets.

2.4 Knowledge Graph Interlinking

Interlinking knowledge graphs, and especially finding links to external entities to establish their identity across the Web, has been one of the paramount problems addressed by the Semantic

²<https://github.com/timrdf/csv2rdf4lod-automation/wiki>, <http://www.w3.org/wiki/ConverterToRdf>

³See <http://grafter.org/>

⁴<https://rdflib.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

Web community [66]. As the original focus of the community was on building and publishing ontologies in a distributed manner, the field of ontology matching emerged as a solution to the problem of their interlinking. Specifically, ontology matching aims at finding correspondences between semantically related entities of different ontologies. These correspondences may stand for equivalence as well as other relations, such as consequence, subsumption, or disjointness, between ontology entities [67]. As the field turned more towards data engineering work with Linked Data and knowledge graphs, the interlinking problem was viewed under the prism of identity resolution, i.e. to find semantically identical entities among different RDF knowledge graphs to link through the `owl:sameAs` property [1]. However, such a strong identity definition implies logical entailments sometimes erroneous; various approaches exist to detect such erroneous identity links, by e.g. using network metrics and community detection algorithms [68].

More recently, the interlinking problem has been studied under the prism of knowledge graph link prediction, primarily by using machine learning and neural network architectures [1]. In music, however, graph representations for music are less common, and machine learning has been used in various ways to complete missing information in both symbolic and audio representations, e.g. mining high-level music features [69, 70] or genre classification [71, 72]. Modern neural architectures have also been recently used, both for learning representations and making predictions [73] and for generative models using variational autoencoders, e.g. MusicVAE [74]. Vector embedding similarities on various semantic descriptors are applied for music recommendation and surfacing terminologies in [75, 76]. MIDI-glove⁵ produces embeddings of notes from monophonic MIDI, but generally does not leverage the graph-like representation of music knowledge graphs and therefore its application for link prediction is not straightforward. Graph embedding techniques for music knowledge graph link prediction are, however, much more scarce; the only experiment successfully using them for link prediction is MIDI2vec [25], which we repurpose here for the general problem of link prediction in musical cultural heritage knowledge graphs.

⁵<https://github.com/brangerbriz/midi-glove>

3 Knowledge Graph Construction and Interlinking Framework

In this Section we define the Polifonia’s KG Construction and Interlinking Framework. We establish this framework in a bottom-up fashion: our starting point are the Pilots and the outcomes of the Survey [77], around which we build the support framework of the Pilot Clinics –a weekly rotation meeting for Pilot leaders and WP2 participants to support KG objectives, ontology modelling, and tools, and agree on technical strategies for building the Polifonia Knowledge Graph from the various pilot datasets. This has two goals: (a) understand the technical requirements of building KGs and establish techniques to address them; and (b) understand what are the potential links between the different datasets, and establish techniques to find them at scale. The former is addressed via the Pilot Clinic summaries described below; while the latter is addressed via the INTERLINK pilot (see Section 3.2). Examples on how such a framework could be useful are: how can we integrate diverse, disparate, non-interoperable chord annotation datasets at large scale for further analysis and model-building? How can we automatically complete missing information in symbolic music (e.g. MIDI) collections, such as composer or genre, and create links by leveraging existing patterns in complete examples?

3.1 Support Framework: Pilot Clinics

To support Polifonia’s pilots in the KG construction process and collect common ontological requirements that are fundamental for interlinking their future knowledge graphs, we organised a special discussion forum – the “KG Pilot Clinics”, where pilots were invited to present their work towards the former objectives. Each clinics session focused on a single pilot, and featured the pilot leader as presenter. The following subsections outline the main outcomes of this collaborative effort, the current plans for KG construction, and the lesson learned from the Pilot Clinics.

As a result of the Pilot Clinics reported below, we find that the pilots are at various stages of development, and present different issues and challenges, when it comes to building KGs. All the pilots start their activities toward KG construction with *data collection*, *data digitization* (if the original datasets were not in digital form yet), and *ontology modelling* to understand the classes and relationships of the domain (see D2.1 [3]). However, from this point the pilots diverge in their activities due to the inherent typology of the datasets they work with, which entails different dataset KG construction requirements:

1. **Text pilots.** These are pilots that work with text-intensive, unstructured data mostly in natural language form (CHILD, MEETUPS, MUSICBO)
2. **Structured metadata pilots.** These are pilots that work with structured metadata describing European musical cultural heritage assets, typically aiming at building KGs from spreadsheets (BELLS, ORGANS)

- 3. Symbolic music data pilots.** These are pilots that work with music symbolic representations in their datasets, or music encodings, covering a wide spectrum of formats and representations such as RISM, incipits, ABC, MusicXML, MEI, JSON-LD, MIDI, etc. (TUNES, FACETS, TONALITIES)

Across these pilot dataset typologies, we also identify three orthogonal ontology themes that operate as containers of some of the modules presented in the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON, see D2.1 [3]): pilots that model *music content* (such as notes, chords, tonalities, etc.), pilots that model *music context* (such as events and metadata around a certain musical work), and *music annotations* (such as opinions and theoretical observations that are asserted in a concrete location of a certain musical work, e.g. between the second and the third measure).

3.1.1 CHILD

Focus of the pilot is in supporting music scholars from the formulation of a hypothesis to the discovery and collection of resources relevant to the enquiry. Considering sources such as Listening Experience Database, Archive.org, and the Gutenberg Project, the pilot will develop a system for supporting the retrieval, collection, curation, and exploration of documentary evidence relevance to music and childhood, derived from digitized books. The knowledge extracted from books will be used to populate a dataset of childrens' experiences of music interlinked with encyclopedic knowledge graphs such as DBpedia and Wikidata and with other datasets in the project.

3.1.2 MEETUPS

This pilot focuses on supporting music historians and teachers by providing a Web tool that enables the exploration and visualisation of encounters between people in the musical world in Europe from c.1800 to c.1945, relying on information extracted from public domain books such as biographies, memoirs and travel writing, and open-access databases. Such encounters were particularly significant before the period when musical ideas and influences were widely disseminated through broadcasting and recording technologies, and the collection of data about them will make it possible to trace key points of cultural and musical exchange and dissemination, and meetings that were catalysts for musical change. A knowledge graph of interlinked *Musical Meetups* will constitute the backbone of the pilot, and the social networks emerging from the graph will inform studies in historical musicology scholarship and teaching. It may also reveal unexpected connections and relationships that cast new light on aspects of European music history.

3.1.3 BELLS

The "Bells" pilot aims to create a Knowledge Graph on the historical bell heritage starting from the Italian reality, and specifically, from two regions (Liguria and Emilia Romagna) conceived as pilot examples to be extended, at a later time, to the whole territory at a national level. The specific domain is little investigated in Italy, and the currently available data is quite heterogeneous. The

methodology adopted for the construction of the Bells Knowledge Graph is largely based on the use of the standards developed by the Italian Ministry of Culture for the cataloging of Tangible and Intangible Cultural Heritage. Data is collected from written and oral sources in collaboration with domain experts (musicologists, ethnomusicologists, campanologists) and representatives of the communities of practice (bell ringers). For the development of the correct description methodology, a first database of 100 sound documents of bell musical performance has been established (the documents, all unpublished, are the result of a donation by the ethnomusicologist Mauro Balma, and consist of records collected in Liguria since the 1980s). Another 400 recordings on analogous support have been acquired by the bell ringers' associations, and will be digitised during the project. Starting from the localisation of the collected recordings, Bells pilot's team is currently carrying out the description of the tangible and intangible entities connected to the sounds (e.g. bells used in the sound performance, bell tower in which they are contained) through the use of specific description models. In particular, the catalogue records that are used are of the following three types: (i) A- architecture, used to describe the Bell Towers and the building to which they are connected (civil buildings or religious buildings); (ii) SM-musical instruments, for the description of bells and bell concerts (polyorganic instruments composed of several bells); (iii) BDI-intangible demo-ethno-anthropological assets, for the description of musical performances. Starting from the recordings, sound practices related to each sound recording are described, as well as the techniques used (cordette, keyboard, etc.), the actors involved, the occasions of execution (religious or civil or undetermined occasions), and so forth. The description models are progressively enriched through the integration of existing vocabularies, in cooperation with the domain experts. The pilot's team is currently working on the description of:

- 100 sound documents and related performances;
- 80 musical instruments (bells / bell concerts) connected to the recordings;
- 80 architectures (bell towers and related buildings) connected to recordings and the bells.

In addition, authority records relating to the historic foundries which produced the catalogued bells will be compiled. The first step is to complete the description activity and publish data through the SigecWeb cataloguing system, currently in use at ICCD. Data stored in our database, called SIGECweb, is published via OAI-PMH protocol¹ in XML format.

The Italian CNR developed a procedure called RDFizer that converts the XML sheets in RDF according to ArCo ontologies. The RDFizer module is documented online.² The result in RDF format is visible at <https://dati.beniculturali.it/lodview-arco/resource/ArchitecturalOrLandscapeHeritage/0700110834.html>.

The result in ICCD website is available here: <https://www.catalogo.beniculturali.it/detail/ArchitecturalOrLandscapeHeritage/0700110834>.

In this way, the data relating to the Historical Bells Heritage can flow into the Polifonia portal but also feed the Italian Catalogue of Cultural Assets (<https://www.catalogo.beniculturali.it/>) and other local projects aimed at enhancing this heritage which is strictly connected to local, national and European traditions and intangible heritage.

¹<http://www.catalogo-old.beniculturali.it/oaitarget/OAIHandler?verb=ListSets>

²<https://github.com/ICCD-MiBACT/ArCo/tree/master/ArCo-release/rdfizer>

3.1.4 ORGANS

The mission of this pilot is to create Knowledge Graphs about the specification, construction practises, and historical information of organs – as most of this knowledge can only be found in (undigitised) bibliographic sources. To create these KGs, ORGANS has been focusing on two research directions: (i) digitisation and textual analysis of the *Orgelencyclopedie* (1997-2010), a 15 volume, 4,500+ pages encyclopaedia containing histories and images of almost 2,000 Dutch organs; (ii) design and development of the ORGANS ontology module, based on the PipeOrgan³ online database. Similarly to other pilots, one the main challenges of ORGANS concerns the automatic KG creation from text retrieved from *Orgelencyclopedie*.

3.1.5 TUNES

The pilot focuses on identifying the origin of tunes, starting from music collections that cover the transition from modal to tonal music (thus overlapping with TONALITIES). The focal point of TUNES is the Dutch Song Database maintained by the Meertens Instituut (Amsterdam), which includes thousands of melodies from Dutch popular culture, spanning a period of more than five centuries. To trace possible international origins of Dutch early popular music culture, this pilot is working on interlinking the Dutch Song Database with a large number of other European collections. These include: RISM, ABC collections, NEUMA, Barlow and Morgenstern, the Early American Secular Music and Its European Sources (American incipits from 1589 to 1839), the ESaC Folk Song Databases (alias the Essen Folk Song Collection EFSC), and Bach Chorales. Nevertheless, except RISM and NEUMA, all the other collections are currently not released as Linked Data, and some of them are only available as unstructured data scattered across the Web. Therefore, most work so far has focused on the analysis of the ontological requirements needed to create KGs out of such collections, based on the reuse and the extension of PON's modules. It is envisaged that the linked melodic datasets resulting from this process will be highly valuable for musicologists and music historians interested in cultural evolution of musical style and in oral transmission and variation.

3.1.6 FACETS

The FACETS pilot aims at providing a system to explore large collections of music-related data, under the assumption that this data is centered on fine-grained music content representation. The pilot targets in particular collections of *encoded scores*, represented either as MusicXML or MEI documents, from which music content can be extracted and linked to external meta-data such as composers, styles, periods, etc. The vision is that of a system that would allow on-line search, classification, and navigation through large collections, exploiting links to discover and organize specific subsets relevant to the user's needs.

³<https://pipeorgan.nl>

A core requirement is to enable music content representation as first-level concepts in the KG of Polifonia. During the pilot clinics, we exposed to our partners an approach that would leverage the content of XML-encoded documents to concise and well-structured knowledge-based information. In order to produce “semantic” data and link this data with other sources (annotations), our modeling approach consists in identifying what is the meaningful content encoded in a score for *music processing applications*, i.e., applications that use encoded scores as input for purposes that are not concerned with details pertaining to (human) readability. The main assumption in this context is that we can safely ignore all layout-related aspects embedded in the score, which can then simply be considered as “noise” from the application viewpoint.

We thus work on the assumption that there is a subset of the data found in score encodings that contains the sufficient and necessary content for such applications. We currently model the structure of this subset as a *MusicNotation* ontology (<http://cedric.cnam.fr/isid/ontologies/files/MusicNote.html>) extending an earlier work [78].

Practically speaking, a MEI document for instance (or MusicXML, or MIDI) would be the source from which one extracts an instance of the score ontology, integrated in the Polifonia knowledge graph, and interlinked with other sources (e.g., a list of composers, a taxonomy of music genres, etc.). We maintain (together with the *IRéMus* partner) a large collection (more than 20K) of encoded scores in MEI in the Neuma platform (<http://neuma.huma-num.fr>). We will supply API endpoints to export JSON-LD instances of this scores. These endpoints will be added to Cornucopia to make sure data can be retrieved by INTERLINK, and inserted in the Polifonia KG. Further work with our partners will link this exported data to existing knowledge, either via explicit references (e.g., composers URI) or implicit one (e.g., analytic pattern extraction to infer the genre, keys, ambitus, etc.)

3.1.7 TONALITIES

Starting from the Sethus Persona and the research problem described in the "Conflicting Theoretical Interpretations" Story, Tonalities has contributed to WP2 by modeling two historical theories related to modal polyphony: Zarlino 1558 and Praetorius 1619. We aim to use these models to infer modes in polyphonic works of the Renaissance. Our ambition is also to verify to what extent the different theories affect the modal classification of a work. In order to achieve these objectives, Tonalities has developed, in collaboration with the OD team, an ontology of analyses that relates a) musical works, b) theoretical models and c) analytical results. Each work is linked to one or several analyses for which are specified: the theoretical models applied, the origin of the analytical information (either manual with an identification of the analyst or mechanical with an identification of the algorithms and their versions), the dates of creation and revision, the thread of discussion to which an analysis gave rise, and finally the analytical results themselves. The knowledge graph of the analyses is fed both from manual annotations made from an annotation interface under construction and from python routines. These routines are based on the toolbox *music21* to extract musical knowledge (ambitus, clefs, keys, scales, melodic formulas, cadences) and on the *Owlready2* package to inject the information into the knowledge graph. A reasoner (HermiT 1.4.3.456) is used to make modal assignments from the confrontation of the instantiated

Figure 3.1: An example of the interlinking methodology: musical content (through melodic, harmonic, and rhythmic similarity) and metadata-based (same or similar entities) linking.

analytical knowledge and the modal classes. In case of (partial) mismatch between the analytical information and the modeled classes, our strategy is to identify "best guesses" from a statistical verification of converging and diverging assertions. The central issue now consists of integrating the models and the knowledge graph into the PON/PNG. Therefore, we will continue the work undertaken in the ontology clinics to perform the necessary alignment and harmonization work. Another important issue is to reformulate the Story's QCs according to the methodology defined by the OD-team in order to clarify them and align them more explicitly with the ontology.

3.1.8 MUSICBO

The mission of this pilot is to develop a multimodal interface to enable the interactive navigation of music collections and thematic multilingual corpora related to Bologna – the Unesco's City of Music. This includes data in different formats, such texts about musicians from Bologna, geolocated data related to historical buildings, local performances that marked the development of European music, as well as their receptions in Italy and across Europe. At the current state, the pilot has been working in collaboration with WP4 towards the automatic creation of Knowledge Graphs from textual data, using state of the art Natural Language Processing methods.

3.2 Construction and Interlinking Framework: INTERLINK Pilot

The main goal of the INTERLINK pilot is to find, trace and establish links among the datasets contributed by the other pilots (*intra-linking*), and in turn, between the latter and online music databases that can be publicly accessed and queried (*inter-linking*). The nature of such links can

be dual: at the music-context level (semantic), and at the music-content level (intrinsic). Both these directions require two separate methodologies as they entail requirements from two different fields: (i) finding contextually/semantically similar entities and relationships – an *entity linking* problem in the music domain (a notorious task in the Semantic Web field); (ii) computational analysis of the music content to extract latent properties of music that can be shared by different pieces – spanning a number of tasks in Music Information Retrieval. The common denominator for both these directions lies in the generality of the data, and in the machine learning driven technologies that the pilot is putting forth to accomplish the aforementioned desiderata.

Music Content Similarity Linking Finding similarities based on the music content is a challenging task in computational music analysis, as it can potentially involve a number of dimensions, often intertwined, that have both perceptual, psychological, and musicological nature. This is particularly evident when dealing with audio-based methods for music similarity, which make it difficult to trace similarities back to the musical content. For instance, chroma-based features extracted from the music signal capture both harmonic and melodic properties of the music, hence, similarity expressed or learned at this level would struggle to distinguish whether its values should be interpreted as melodic or harmonic similarities. On the other hand, modelling similarities at a semantic level requires explicit explainability of “what” is similar to and “why”.

To address this challenge, INTERLINK is currently developing *Musilar* – a suite of music similarity methods defined over symbolic music and a framework for analysing and evaluating these methods on a collection of benchmark tasks. Differently from audio-based methods, the algorithms included in *Musilar* are defined over specific (symbolic) musical properties, allowing to trace and explain similarities with respect to melody, harmony, and rhythm. At the current state of development, *Musilar* counts two methods for harmonic similarity: the Tonal Pitch Space Distance (TPSD)⁴ from [79], and the Local Harmonic Agreement based on Recurring Patterns (LHARP)⁵. The former is a state of the art method for global harmonic similarity, whereas the latter is a novel algorithm that we contributed for tracing local harmonic similarities. In a similar fashion, similarity will also be expressed with respect to other latent properties of music, which are hierarchically defined on top of melodic, harmonic, and rhythmic components, or even triggered by them. This contributes an additional level of content-based linking, where music can be related based on more complex constructs and properties that originate from the musical surface. Based on our recent achievements, this can already be done for structural complexity [80], thereby enabling the linking of music pieces with similar levels of complexity. Although the latter contribution is defined from the audio, the extraction of structural complexity undergoes a music structure analysis step [81], where symbolic content is produced in terms of structural annotations – thereby ensuring the full explainability of this process for ontological modelling. A similar level of linking will also be established with respect to the emotions that the music can induce into listeners [82], which is also a requirement expressed by the other pilots⁶. By leveraging state of the art methods for

⁴<https://github.com/andreamust/TPSD>

⁵<https://github.com/polifonia-project/lharp>

⁶<https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>

music emotion recognition [83], which can provide a reasonable level of explainability, this will thus enable emotion-based linking of music pieces in the arousal and valence space [84].

Thanks to the ability of tracing content-based similarities in Musilar, and explain the derivation/inference of more abstract musical constructs and properties (structures, emotions), all similarities will be modelled according to the Comparative Measures module in the Polifonia Ontology Network (c.f. Section 3.2.1). This will enrich the Polifonia KG with expressive and meaningful similarity relationships, rather than only introducing flat links among music entities.

Music Metadata Similarity Linking Inferring similarities that can be established outside the musical content is another challenging problem that has been studied for both contextual music data [85] and metadata only [86]. In Polifonia, addressing this direction has initially required a deep understanding of the expected nature of the data that will be provisioned by the other pilots. To enable this interconnection, a new persona and a new story were introduced, according to the new data- and example- driven ontological framework that the Polifonia Ontology Design team has introduced. The new persona, called Linka⁷, has been carefully designed to encompass the ontological requirements that are explicitly, or implicitly shared between the other pilots. The development and the extension of the ontology modules that can address Linka's competency questions thus provide an ontological infrastructure that facilitates the interlinking of pilots' datasets. For instance, the story `Linka#1_MusicKnowledge`⁸ primarily focuses on music cataloguing data – which is a central ontological requirement expressed by most of the pilots.

In the meantime, preliminary work has been carried out to test entity linking methods on datasets shared by Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV). More precisely, NISV's work that follows provided a first direction towards linking datasets with cataloguing information based on string matching methods – which revealed the main challenges and issues of these methods.

NISV knowledge graph. NISV has many music-related collections, which are very different to each other, and are at present hard to find within the larger archive. NISV has developed infrastructure for generating linked data and for displaying that linked data in the [Media Suite portal](#). This offers a good opportunity for testing out the Polifonia principles by generating knowledge graphs for these separate music collections and linking them via person entities. We postulate that this should improve the visibility, accessibility and usability of these collections.

We have inventoried the music collections of NISV. From this inventory, we have identified two collections which are particularly suitable for interlinking. These are the MOZ collection, which contains almost 80,000 radio and TV broadcasts of concerts, and the 78 RPM collection, which contains more than 6,000 commercial music records. These are distinctive collections which nevertheless share many potential links, for example music from a given composer may be recorded on a record and also performed in a concert. The collections have explicit links to persons defined in the [GTAA thesaurus](#) for more than 80% of the items. These persons provide a means of

⁷<https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories/tree/main/Linka:%20Computer%20Scientist>

⁸https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories/blob/main/Linka:%20Computer%20Scientist/Linka%231_MusicKnowledge.md

Figure 3.2: Representing harmonic similarities for content-based linking via Musilar.

interlinking the collections both with each other, and with external sources such as Discogs and MusicBrainz.

The first task will be to publish the linked data of these collections in such a way that they can be selected and queried via SPARQL. The following step will be to interlink them.

A particular issue faced in interlinking these collections with external sources is that of ambiguity. A previous trial of linking part of the GTAA thesaurus to Discogs artists resulted in almost a quarter of a million links, of which almost half were ambiguous. This issue was the subject of a Pilot clinic, in which some possible solutions were identified in literature. INTERLINK and WP2 will work further to find and test solutions for this issue.

Example data from the collections is available in the [Polifonia links repository](#)

3.2.1 Comparative Measure Module

The Comparative Measure is an ontology module of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) which has been introduced in [D2.4] to model similarity relationships at the musical content level.

The module shows great potential for representing novel computed information such as harmonic similarity, complete lyric similarity and lyric similarity (at the sentence level) between two musical pieces, source credibility, etc. Thus far, we have defined a general pattern for this module which can be applied for distinct types of similarities. Figure 3.2 depicts the specialisation of the pattern to represent the harmonic similarities between recordings of two musical pieces. Common information that is presented in all types of similarities are the `similarity function`,

encoding, similarity score, recordings that are involved in the similarity computation. While in the case of the harmonic similarity, there is the `time interval` that is specific to this specialisation because it represents the exact time interval where a harmonic similarity is detected between two musical pieces.

3.2.2 SPARQL Anything Converters and Query Templates

In anticipation of the stories, personas, requirements and competency questions from the pilots above (see also [87] and the online repository⁹), we foresee a number of different datasets with the common need of generating an RDF knowledge graph from their structured sources. Any workflow implementing this needs to support a large variety of data formats, offer flexibility in its data model, and be extensible in case “eccentric” data formats (which are common in music datasets, e.g. JAMS, MEI, MusicXML, iReal, etc.) need to be covered.

SPARQL Anything [20], currently being developed¹⁰ as part of H2020 SPICE¹¹, can offer such flexibility, and we use it in Polifonia as our to-go tool choice for the conversion of structured data into RDF knowledge graphs. SPARQL Anything uses a unique data schema called Facade-X, a simple meta-model that allows converters to produce RDF from diverse data sources without the need of a domain vocabulary. A generic example of a Facade-X data object is shown in Listing 3.1.

```

1
2 @prefix fx: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/ns/> .
3 @prefix xyz: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/data/> .
4 @prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
5
6 [] a fx:Root ;
7   rdf:_1 [
8     xyz:someKey "some value" ;
9     rdf:_1 "another value with unspecified key"
10  ];
11  rdf:_2 [
12    rdf:type xyz:SomeType ;
13    rdf:_1 "another value"
14  ]
15 ] .
    
```

Listing 3.1: Facade-X listing for a meta-model with a list-like structure.

Two additional advantages of SPARQL Anything are that (a) this allows for directly querying any supported file format using SPARQL, through the use of the `SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:>` keyword, effectively maintaining compatibility with the SPARQL standard; and (b) it allows the construction of knowledge graphs through the standard `CONSTRUCT` SPARQL keyword (which returns an RDF graph, instead of returning a table as it is common using `SELECT`).

⁹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>

¹⁰See online repository at <https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/sparql.anything>

¹¹<https://spice-h2020.eu/>

Therefore, in Polifonia we build RDF knowledge graphs by extending SPARQL Anything in three ways:

- We implement data converters to support yet unsupported structured file formats that are specifically relevant for the Polifonia datasets, namely MIDI, MusicXML, MEI, ABC, or any other music representation format for which querying and knowledge graph construction may be required. If the music dataset formats are currently supported (e.g. JSON), we simply reuse them
- We implement Facade-X templates (as e.g. shown in Listing 3.1) to support the models and representations contained in the aforementioned file formats. For example, JSON can be queried with a current converter, but if the target JSON file contains a JAMS¹² music annotation data structure, a Facade-X and a query template may be needed. An example of such a template is given later in this deliverable (see Listing 4.3).
- We design and deploy data transformation pipelines on top of SPARQL Anything when necessary. This may be needed if, for example, the source dataset is contained in various thousands of files in various directories, distributed sources, or various formats. An example of such a pipeline is described in Section 4.1.1.

3.2.3 Interlinking Framework

To discover links between different music knowledge graphs, we follow two different approaches:

- **Heuristic-based linking.** Whenever music knowledge graphs provide sufficient fine-grained information, and are of a tractable size, we propose heuristics for finding missing links between them. For example, if high-quality metadata is available in both the source and the target music knowledge graph (e.g. both contain names of bands and titles of songs), then we attempt to use simple baseline heuristics, such as string similarity algorithms like Levenshtein distance [88], over a coherent concatenation of the values of such metadata properties. Similarly, if both the source and the target music knowledge graphs contain IDs to external datasets (e.g. MusicBrainz [5]), then we attempt to complete their URIs and verify they de-reference valid resources.
- **Music Knowledge Graph Link Prediction.** When no simple heuristics can be foreseen, we discover links by re-interpreting the problem of music knowledge interlinking as a knowledge graph link prediction problem. In particular, we use graph embeddings methods [89, 25] over symbolic music content to learn distributional properties of music and their relationships with highly-correlated resources in other knowledge graphs. An example of this is the MIDI2vec algorithm [25], which we describe in Chapter 4 and plan to extend for general symbolic music knowledge graph interlinking.

As for the collections that will be interlinked, on one hand these include pilot-specific data such as the Dutch Song Database¹³ (TUNES pilot) and the NEUMA digital library [90] (FACETS pilot),

¹²[urlhttps://jams.readthedocs.io/en/stable/](https://jams.readthedocs.io/en/stable/)

¹³<http://www.liederenbank.nl/index.php?lan=en>

along with the 78 RPM collection – contributed by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV); but also, MIR datasets and music knowledge graphs providing melodic content – such as the MIDI LD [11], and harmonic/chordal content from the newly contributed Chord Corpus (c.f. Section 4.1.1). Finally, to address a recurring need that is common to most pilots, music cataloguing data will also be linked to MusicBrainz¹⁴ and Discogs¹⁵.

¹⁴<https://musicbrainz.org>

¹⁵<https://www.discogs.com>

4 Evaluation

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph Construction and Interlinking frameworks described in Chapter 3, we show here their direct application to two use cases among the various Polifonia pilots: **ChoCo-KG**, and **MIDI2vec**. We consider the methodology summarised in the previous chapter through the INTERLINK pilot, summarised in Figure 3.1, and we instantiate it in two specific use cases on chord data (musical harmony) and MIDI knowledge graph completion and link discovery.

These two use cases are good representatives of the full collection of datasets that we expect to represent as Knowledge Graphs and interlink in Polifonia (see Chapter 3). First, and foremost, the original symbolic music collections in which both ChoCo and MIDI2vec are based on –documented in Section 5– are very rich in European music cultural heritage. The ChoCo original datasets¹ cover chord annotations in a wide spectrum of European music history: from the late classic/early romantic eras in the Schubert-Winterreise dataset (18th-19th centuries), to modern transcriptions of jazz (Real Book, JAAH, etc.), rock (Rock Corpus, Isophonics) and European folk (Nottingham). Similarly, the MIDI collections in which MIDI2vec is based on [25] are very rich in European music history, containing e.g. classical music transcriptions (SLAC, MuseData) as well as contemporary music (movie and videogame soundtracks). Although admittedly these two use cases focus on two specific domains (harmonic data integration through knowledge graphs, and link prediction in MIDI data), we consider them here as canonical examples for other datasets in the project (e.g. TONALITIES, FACETS, BELLS, ORGANS, etc.) that could follow up on the techniques presented here. We, therefore, point at their vast and challenging variety as an asset and an opportunity to generalise these techniques to the broader project.

ChoCo-KG is a full-fledged Polifonia Knowledge Graph of 30M+ RDF triples representing musical chord annotations integrating 18 different existing datasets, and constitutes a canonical case for music knowledge graph construction, leveraging modules of the Polifonia Ontology Network [3] that deal with one of the three big Polifonia themes/global modelling needs, *annotations* (the others being *content* and *patterns*). MIDI2vec is an approach for using music knowledge graph embeddings for knowledge graph link prediction (interlinking), that accurately finds links between a music knowledge graph and resources from other knowledge graphs when trained with sufficient and high-quality annotations.

4.1 ChoCo-KG: The Chord Corpus Knowledge Graph Construction

In music, *chords* are sets of multiple notes that are heard as if played simultaneously, and in Western music convey notions of musical consonance (pleasant, euphonious, beautiful) or dis-

¹See <https://github.com/jonnybluesman/choco/blob/main/README.md>

sonance (unpleasant, discordant, rough) when they are heard by the human ear. For example, the chord $B\flat^{7(\#9)}$ consists of 5 simultaneous notes: $B\flat$, D, F, $A\flat$, and $D\flat$, and has a startling, dissonant, and irresolute jazzy sound. Chords are the basic foundation of musical harmony –the process by which overlapping sounds are analysed by hearing–, and their properties are well studied in musicology (see, e.g. [91] for an extensive introduction). For example, the distances between notes (or intervals) in the chord $B\flat^{7(\#9)}$ are the root ($B\flat$), its major third, its fifth, its seventh, and its augmented ninth. These intervals characterise the harmonic properties of chords, and their symbolic representation makes them particularly well suited for musicological analysis in terms of their identification and co-occurrence patterns in music.

A large number of different chord notations exist (Harte, Roman, ABC, Lead sheet, etc.), each with different levels of expressiveness, in a large number of disconnected chord datasets that are hard to combine. This poses a challenge for combining existing chord datasets into larger ones, which is required by modern techniques such as deep learning for tasks like chord recognition and music generation [73]. Other existing approaches address this by typically focusing on scale, and publish large numbers of chord annotations. For example, UltimateGuitar² offers a collection of 1.1M songs annotated by a community of 12M musicians. Chordify addresses the challenge of scalable chord annotation by applying methods for automated chord estimation (e.g. Tonal Pitch Step Distance [92], generative grammars [93]). However, none of these approaches solves the problem of semantically integrating chord annotation datasets with (a) sufficiently high quality for downstream tasks; (b) precise timing information; (c) through an open license; (d) using different chord notations; and (e) at large scale. The problem is exacerbated by the lack of a standard music annotation format. Although the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) community has proposed and used JAMS (JSON Annotated Music Specification) [94] to uniformly represent music annotations, combined efforts of MIR and Semantic Web researchers to address chord annotation data interoperability have been scarce.

For these reasons, in Polifonia we have worked towards using Semantic Web technologies and Knowledge Graphs to integrate large collections of timed, high-quality and openly available chord annotation data, in the so-called **Chord Corpus (ChoCo) Knowledge Graph (ChoCo-KG)**. Through an intensive data workflow, we curate, transform, and integrate more than 21,100 human-made, high-quality chord-related annotations from 18 highly heterogeneous chord datasets, following the JAMS data structure annotation model. The annotations are rich in provenance data (e.g. metadata of the annotated work, authors of annotations, etc.) and refer to both symbolic music notation and audio recordings. We re-publish and enrich these annotations with the ChoCo ontology and Knowledge Graph presented here, providing fine-grained semantic descriptions of chords, opportunities for chord interoperability, and 3,000+ links to external datasets. We also show evidence of interest and use of the ChoCo-KG, and postulate its value for the Semantic Web and MIR communities at enabling the study of harmony through large scale graphs.

²<https://www.ultimate-guitar.com/>

Partition	Type	Notation	Original format	Annotations	Genres	Ref
Isophonics	A	Harte	JAMS	300	pop, rock	[95]
JAAH	S	Harte	JSON	113	jazz	[96]
Schubert-Winterreise	A, S	Harte	csv	25 (S), 25*9 (A)	classical	[97]
Billboard	A	Harte	LAB, txt	890 (740)	pop	[98]
Chordify	A	Harte	JAMS	50*4	pop	[99]
Robbie Williams	A	Harte	LAB, txt	61	pop	[100]
The Real Book	S	Harte	LAB	2486	jazz	[101]
Uspop 2002	A	Harte	LAB	195	pop	[102]
RWC-Pop	A	Harte	LAB	100	pop	[103]
Weimar Jazz Database	S	Leadsheet	SQL	456	jazz	[104]
Wikifonia	S	Leadsheet	xml	6500+	various	-
iReal Pro	S	Leadsheet	iReal	2000+	various	-
Band-in-a-Box	S	Leadsheet	mgu, sku	5000+	various	[79]
When in Rome	S	Roman	RomanText	450	classical	[105]
Rock Corpus	S	Roman	har	200	rock	[106]
Mozart Piano Sonata	S	Roman	DCMLab	54 (18)	classical	[107]
Jazz Corpus	S	Hybrid	txt	76	jazz	[108]
Nottingham	S	ABC	ABC	1000+	folk	[109]

Table 4.1: Overview of the 18 chord datasets currently included in ChoCo. Letters “A” and “S” are used to denote *audio* and *symbolic* annotations, respectively.

4.1.1 Knowledge Graph Construction Workflow

We describe here the resources contained in the ChoCo Knowledge Graph, as they are derived from the ChoCo dataset and the JAMS ontology. All code, data, and related resources are available online at <https://github.com/jonnybluesman/choco>, allowing for full reproducibility of the corpus creation. The general workflow is illustrated in Figure 4.1 and detailed in the following subsections.

4.1.1.1 Chordal data in ChoCo

Table 4.1 summarises the source chord datasets (partitions) that are integrated as part of ChoCo. At the current stage, ChoCo comprehends 18 high-quality chord datasets providing timed annotations of chord progressions in different formats (e.g. lab, csv, txt, xml), notations (e.g. Harte, Leadsheet, Roman, ABC), and types (audio, symbolic). The rich and diversified nature of this resource, encompassing several genres/styles and periods, makes it the largest chord collection of its kind – with more than 21K annotated progressions. ChoCo’s partitions can be categorised according to their chord notation system.

Figure 4.1: Conversion workflow to create the ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph.

4.1.1.2 From chordal data to JAMS datasets

The first challenge of bringing together existing chord datasets into a coherent, uniform corpus is the variety of formats in which chord annotations, and other related information, are encoded. In order to address this issue, we leverage the popular JAMS data structure [94] as a simple, content-agnostic wrapper for expressing music annotations in general, and chord annotations in particular. JAMS relies on the popular Web data exchange JSON format, and enforces the following structure based on three basic properties³:

1. `file_metadata`, describing the music piece these annotations refer to. More precisely, it contains the following properties:
 - `identifiers`, optionally providing explicit links to external resources, mostly relating to cataloguing information from e.g. MusicBrainz;
 - `artist`, `title`, `release`, where the former usually refers to the performer or band, and the latter is intended as a more general definition of album;
 - `duration`, defining a temporal span within which annotations can fall.

³See <https://jams.readthedocs.io/> for additional details.

2. `annotations`, a container of annotation objects, each describing a specific *namespace*⁴ that identifies the type of the annotation's subject (e.g., chords, structural segments, emotions, patterns, keys, etc.). These annotations also include metadata to document the annotation process (e.g. whether the annotation is manually produced or inferred by an algorithmic method, the name of the annotator or software, information about the annotation tools, rules and validation).
3. `sandbox`, described as an unrestricted place to store any additional data.

Listings 4.1 and 4.2 show excerpts of an example JAMS file from the Isophonics collection [95] annotating chords for Queen's *Bohemian Rhapsody*.

```

1 {
2   "sandbox": {},
3   "annotations": [
4     {
5       "data": [
6         {
7           "duration": 0.459,
8           "confidence": 1.0,
9           "value": "N",
10          "time": 0.0
11        },
12        {
13          "duration": 3.663,
14          "confidence": 1.0,
15          "value": "Bb:maj6",
16          "time": 0.459
17        },
18        {
19          "duration": 0.789,
20          "confidence": 1.0,
21          "value": "C:7",
22          "time": 4.122
23        },
24        ...
25      ],
26    },
27  ]
28 }
```

Listing 4.1: Excerpt of the three first chords in a JAMS file annotating Queen's *Bohemian Rhapsody*.

```

1   "annotation_metadata": {
2     "annotation_tools": "",
3     "curator": {
4       "name": "Matthias Mauch",
5       "email": "m.mauch@qmul.ac.uk"
6     },
7     "annotator": {},
8     "version": 1.0,
9     "corpus": "Isophonics",
10    "annotation_rules": "",
11    "validation": "",
12    "data_source": ""
13  },
14  "namespace": "chord",
15  "sandbox": {}
16 }, ... ],
17 "file_metadata": {
18   "jams_version": "0.2.0",
19   "title": "01 Bohemian Rhapsody",
20   "identifiers": {},
21   "release": "",
22   "duration": 358.293,
23   "artist": "Queen"
24 }
25 }
```

Listing 4.2: Annotation and file metadata in a JAMS file annotating Queen's *Bohemian Rhapsody*.

Although JAMS has an implicit focus for audio-based annotations, its definition and structure are flexible enough to be easily extendable to the symbolic domain. This is also confirmed by the modular design of the codebase, where additional namespaces can be registered by a user, by simply providing regular expressions to validate the annotation content (e.g. a new chord notation). In other words, any arbitrary music annotation can be described within JAMS as long as the atomic observations (e.g. the individual occurrences of chords making up the progression) are described in terms of: `time`, a temporal anchor specifying the onset of the observation; `duration`, `value` (e.g. *Bb:maj7*), and `confidence`, a scalar in $[0, 1]$ expressing a level of certainty by the annotator (or algorithm). Therefore, the only elements distinguishing audio from symbolic annotations, are the temporal specifications (time and duration), which are described in

⁴The term namespace in JAMS has a different sense than a Web namespace.

absolute (seconds) or metrical (measure and beat/offset) terms, respectively.

4.1.1.2.1 Jamification of datasets Considering the rich diversity of annotation formats and conventions for data organisation (the way content is scattered across folders, files, database tables, etc.), each chord dataset in ChoCo (c.f. Table 4.1) undergoes a standardisation process finalised to the creation of a JAMS dataset. This is needed to aggregate all relevant annotations of a piece (chord, keys, etc.) in a single JAMS file, and to extract content metadata from relevant sources.

The content metadata of a (music) dataset is indeed crucial to identify, describe and retrieve the actual musical content being annotated. This typically includes the title of each piece, artists (composers and/or performers), and cataloguing information (album/release or collected work), ideally with the provision of identifiers (e.g. MusicBrainz IDs). Nevertheless, only the *Mozart Piano Sonata* collection [107] explicitly provides complete content metadata in a `csv` file, as usually expected from a music dataset. When content metadata is missing, this needs to be found online (HTML pages, supplementary material), from articles/reports documenting the collection, by resolving any cross-reference among files and dataset-specific identifiers, extracted from the actual score (or better, the dataset-specific representation of the score), or inferred from the organisation of files in folders (e.g. `Michael Jackson/Essential Michael Jackson [Disc 01]/1-16_Beat_it.lab` indicates author, album, disc, track number, and title respectively) – which vastly varies from dataset to dataset due to the lack of a “datasheet for datasets” in the music domain [110]. The same applies to the extraction, pre-processing, and standardisation of harmonic annotations from these collections, some of which were never released as chord datasets (*Weimar Jazz Database*, *Wikifonia*, *iReal Pro*, *Nottingham*). As each partition entails a combination of all the latter dimensions (different organisation of content and metadata, different annotation formats and conventions), this step required considerable efforts – which already improves the usability of these resources for music researchers, and drastically simplifies the KG construction process.

In sum, following the standardisation process, each of these 18 JAMS datasets represents a novel contribution per se, due to the heterogeneity of annotation formats and practises, and the limited availability of content metadata in their original version. This also includes those collections with annotations already released in JAMS format; for example, JAMS files in *CASD* do not include local key annotations, which need to be retrieved from *Billboard*; and *Isophonics* does not provide content metadata which is implicitly encoded in the folder structure.

4.1.1.3 The JAMS Ontology and the Choco Knowledge Graph

To represent JAMS annotations as a Knowledge Graph we design an ontology that formally represents the JAMS data model. The JAMS ontology is part of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON), from which we can reuse several classes and properties. Furthermore, we reuse the Chord ontology [111] for modeling chords according to the Harte data model. We also use resources from the PON Musical Feature ontology module (e.g. `mf:Chord`) to represent chords

and their related information.

Our general ontological requirements can be summarised as follows:

- the resulting KG must encode JAMS files and JAMS annotations as such, keeping all provenance and process-related information: e.g. source dataset, annotator, confidence, etc.
- the KG must distinguish the performers, who are properties of a track/score, from the composers/authors of a track, which are properties of its corresponding musical composition
- temporal information must be expressed according to the type of the annotation's subject, i.e. audio or score
- chords must be modelled according to the data model of the most common chord notations: Harte, Roman, and Polychord

Figure 4.2: Fragment of the JAMS ontology describing JAMS files and their provenance, musical objects and JAMS annotations. We use the Graffoo notation: yellow boxes are classes, blue/green arrows are object/datatype properties, purple circles are individuals, green polygons are datatypes.

Figure 4.2 shows a fragment of the JAMS ontology. On the left (box A) we define the classes for representing scores (`mf:Score`), recordings (tracks) (`mf:Recording`), and musical compositions (`mf:MusicalComposition`). This distinction is important to express when scores and tracks refer to the same song (i.e. musical composition), through the properties `mc:hasScore` and `mp:recordingOf`. Furthermore, musical compositions can be a hub for reconciling data

from other musical knowledge graphs. For example, from the midi linked data cloud [11] we link midi files to their corresponding musical compositions. The class `core:Agent` is used to link authors/composers to musical compositions (`mc:hasComposer`) and performers to scores or recordings (`mp:performedBy`).

Addressing interoperability of chord representations: - Reuse of Chord ontology for Harte - Mini ontology for roman numerals - Mini ontology for polychords

Other resources: - Ontologies in PON for file metadata

Knowledge Graph construction. To build the ChoCo Knowledge Graph (ChoCo KG) we propose `jams2rdf`, an open-source tool to convert any JAMS file to RDF, with the following usage: `jams2rdf.py <input_jams_file> [<output_rdf_file>]`. If no output RDF file is specified triples are sent to `stdout`. `jams2rdf` relies on *SPARQL Anything* [112], an approach to query anything (i.e. data in any file format) directly using SPARQL in a standards-compliant way. Leveraging SPARQL Anything's JSON module, we propose a SPARQL `CONSTRUCT` query template (Listing 4.3) that generates ChoCo triples according to the ChoCo ontology (Figure 4.2). This allows for a modular design, as different conceptualisations, ontologies and tripleifications for JAMS can be added in separate, independent SPARQL queries. Besides queries needed for building the ChoCo KG, we publish additional ones useful to extract and manipulate specific JAMS fields.⁵ To build the ChoCo KG, we iteratively run `jams2rdf` using the query template over our entire collection of curated JAMS files. This yields 31,404,857 RDF triples.

```

1 PREFIX xyz: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/data/>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fx: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/ns/>
5 # PREFIX choco-d: <http://purl.org/choco/data/>
6 PREFIX jams: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/jams/>
7 PREFIX mp: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-performance/>
8 PREFIX mf: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-features/>
9 PREFIX mc: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-composition/>
10 PREFIX core: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/core/>
11 PREFIX pon-resource: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/>
12 PREFIX prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#>
13 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
14 PREFIX roman: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/roman/>
15 PREFIX poly: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/polychord/>
16 PREFIX chord: <http://purl.org/ontology/chord/>
17
18
19 CONSTRUCT {
20     # the file from which the data is extracted
21     jams:foo a jams:JAMSFile ;
22         jams:jamsVersion ?jams_version ;
23         jams:identifiers ?ids ; # TO DO: process object, this will always be a BN
24         jams:release ?release ;
25         prov:wasDerivedFrom ?corpus ;
26         prov:wasMemberOf <https://github.com/jonnybluesman/choco> .
27
28     # COMPOSITION
29     pon-resource:MusicalComposition%2Fsong_local_id a mc:MusicalComposition ;
30         rdfs:label ?title ;
31         prov:wasDerivedFrom jams:foo ;
32         # only if the sandbox.type = score

```

⁵See <https://github.com/jonnybluesman/choco/tree/main/choco/queries>

```

33         ?composer_type_relation pon-resource:Agent%2Fartist_local_id .
34
35     # ARTIST
36     pon-resource:Agent%2Fartist_local_id ?composer_is_type core:Agent ;
37         rdfs:label ?composer_name .
38
39     # ARTIST
40     pon-resource:Agent%2Fartist_local_id ?performer_is_type core:Agent ;
41         rdfs:label ?performer_name .
42
43     # RECORDING to create if audio or performer
44     pon-resource:Recording%2Frecording_local_id ?recording_is_type mp:Recording ;
45         ?recording_title ?title ;
46         ?recording_label ?title ;
47         ?is_recording_of pon-resource:MusicalComposition%2Fsong_local_id ;
48         ?recording_duration ?duration ;
49         ?recording_contained_in ?release ;
50         # only if the sandbox.type = audio
51         ?performer_type_relation pon-resource:Agent%2Fartist_local_id ;
52         ?recording_derived_from jams:foo .
53
54     # SCORE
55     # if it a score, we create a score individual and its description (duration, provenance)
56     pon-resource:Score%2Fscore_local_id ?is_score_of pon-resource:MusicalComposition%2Fsong_local_id ;
57         ?score_type mf:Score ;
58         ?score_label ?title ;
59         ?score_derived_from jams:foo ;
60         ?score_duration ?duration ;
61         ?score_of pon-resource:MusicalComposition%2Fsong_local_id ;
62         ?performer_no_audio pon-resource:Agent%2Fartist_local_id.
63
64     # ANNOTATION
65     ?annotation_uri a jams:JAMSAnnotation ;
66         a ?jams_annotation_type ;
67         jams:hasValidityDuration ?annotation_duration ;
68         ?score_annotation_valid_from ?metrical_time_uri_annotation ;
69         ?audio_annotation_valid_from ?annotation_time ;
70         jams:includesObservation ?observation_uri .
71
72     # ANNOTATOR
73     pon-resource:Agent%2Fannotator_local_id a core:Agent ;
74         jams:hasName ?annotator_name ;
75         jams:hasAnnotatorType ?annotator_type_uri ;
76         rdfs:label ?annotator_name .
77
78     # ANNOTATION METRICAL TIME (only for SCORE)
79     ?metrical_time_uri_annotation a jams:MetricalTime ;
80         ?score_start_measure ?annotation_duration ; #TODO decompose the score value with a regex
81         ?score_start_offset ?annotation_duration ;
82         ?score_start_beat ?annotation_duration .
83
84     # OBSERVATION
85     ?observation_uri a jams:JAMSObservation,
86         ?observation_type, ?occurrence_type ;
87         jams:hasConfidence ?confidence ;
88         jams:hasDuration ?observation_duration ;
89         ?score_observation_starts_at ?metrical_time_uri_observation ;
90         ?audio_observation_starts_at ?observation_time ;
91         jams:ofChord ?chord_uri.
92
93     # OBSERVATION METRICAL TIME (only for SCORE)
94     ?metrical_time_uri_observation a jams:MetricalTime ;
95         ?score_start_measure ?observation_time ; #TODO decompose the score value with a regex
96         ?score_start_offset ?observation_time ;
    
```

```

97         ?score_start_beat ?observation_time .
98     }
99     WHERE {
100         SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:file://%FILEPATH%> {
101
102             # ?f xyz:file%5Fmetadata ?file_metadata .
103             # ?file_metadata xyz:title ?title .
104             # ?f fx:anySlot ?s .
105
106             # ?file a fx:root .
107             #####
108             # SANDBOX
109             # check wether the annotation refers to a score or an audio object
110             # the value is stored in the main sandbox
111             ?x xyz:sandbox ?sandbox .
112             ?sandbox xyz:type ?object_type .
113             OPTIONAL {?sandbox xyz:performer ?performer_list .
114             ?performer_list fx:anySlot ?performer .
115             ?performer xyz:name ?performer_name .}
116             OPTIONAL {?sandbox xyz:composer ?composer_list .
117             ?composer_list fx:anySlot ?composer .
118             ?composer xyz:name ?composer_name .}
119
120             # TODO: infer the artist type from the sandbox type
121             OPTIONAL {
122                 FILTER (?composer != "")
123                 BIND (mc:hasComposer AS ?composer_type_relation)
124                 BIND (rdf:type AS ?composer_is_type)
125             }
126             OPTIONAL {
127                 FILTER (?performer != "")
128                 BIND (mp:performedBy AS ?performer_type_relation)
129                 BIND (rdf:type AS ?performer_is_type)
130             }
131
132             OPTIONAL {
133                 FILTER (?object_type = "score")
134                 # BIND (mc:hasComposer AS ?composer_type_relation)
135                 BIND (mc:isScoreOf AS ?is_score_of)
136                 BIND (rdf:type AS ?score_type)
137                 BIND (rdfs:label AS ?score_label)
138                 BIND (mf:duration AS ?score_duration)
139                 BIND (mc:isScoreOf AS ?score_of)
140                 # annotation time information
141                 BIND (jams:annotationValidFrom AS ?score_annotation_valid_from)
142                 BIND (jams:hasMeasure AS ?score_start_measure)
143                 BIND (jams:hasOffset AS ?score_start_offset)
144                 BIND (jams:hasBeat AS ?score_start_beat)
145                 BIND (jams:JAMSScoreObservation AS ?observation_type)
146                 # observation
147                 # BIND (rdf:type AS ?observation_time_score)
148             }
149
150             OPTIONAL {
151                 FILTER (?object_type = "audio")
152                 # BIND (mp:performedBy AS ?performer_type_relation)
153                 BIND (rdf:type AS ?recording_is_type)
154                 BIND (mc:hasTitle AS ?recording_title)
155                 BIND (mc:recordingOf AS ?is_recording_of)
156                 BIND (mc:label AS ?recording_label)
157                 BIND (mc:duration AS ?recording_duration)
158                 BIND (mp:recordingContainedIn AS ?recording_contained_in)
159                 BIND (prov:wasDerivedFrom AS ?recording_derived_from)
160                 # annotation time information

```

```

161         BIND (jams:hasValidityStartingTime AS ?audio_annotation_valid_from)
162         BIND (jams:JAMSAudioObservation AS ?observation_type)
163         BIND (jams:performedBy AS ?performer_no_audio)
164         # observation
165         # BIND (rdf:type AS ?observation_time_audio)
166     }
167
168     #####
169     # ANNOTATIONS
170     #####
171     BIND (IF (?object_type = "score", jams:JAMSScoreAnnotation, jams:JAMSAudioAnnotation) AS ?jams_annotation
172     ?x xyz:annotations ?jams_annotations .
173     ?jams_annotations fx:anySlot ?annotation_properties .
174     ?annotation_properties xyz:namespace ?namespace .
175     ?annotation_properties xyz:sandbox ?annotation_sandbox .
176     ?annotation_properties xyz:annotation%5Fmetadata ?annotation_metadata .
177     ?annotation_properties xyz:time ?annotation_time .
178     ?annotation_properties xyz:duration ?annotation_duration .
179     ?annotation_properties xyz:data ?data .
180     BIND (IF (?namespace = "key_mode", jams:ScoreKeyModeOccurrence, jams:ScoreChordOccurrence) AS ?occurrence
181
182     #####
183     # ANNOTATION METADATA
184     #####
185     ?annotation_metadata xyz:annotation%5Ftools ?tools .
186     ?annotation_metadata xyz:curator ?curator .
187     ?curator xyz:name ?curator_name .
188     ?curator xyz:email ?curator_email .
189     ?annotation_metadata xyz:annotator ?annotator .
190     ?annotator xyz:name ?annotator_name .
191     ?annotator xyz:annotator%5Ftype ?annotator_type .
192     # get the annotator type URI
193     OPTIONAL {
194         FILTER (?annotator_type = "program")
195         BIND (pon-resource:annotator-program AS ?annotator_type_uri)
196     # TODO: change placeholder IRI
197     }
198     OPTIONAL {
199         FILTER (?annotator_type = "expert_human")
200         BIND (pon-resource:annotator-expert-human AS ?annotator_type_uri)
201     # TODO: change placeholder IRI
202     }
203     OPTIONAL {
204         FILTER (?annotator_type = "crowdsourcing")
205         BIND (pon-resource:annotator-crowdsourcing AS ?annotator_type_uri)
206     # TODO: change placeholder IRI
207     }
208     OPTIONAL {
209         FILTER (?annotator_type = "")
210         BIND (" " AS ?annotator_type_uri)
211     }
212     ?annotation_metadata xyz:version ?version .
213     ?annotation_metadata xyz:corpus ?corpus .
214     ?annotation_metadata xyz:annotation%5Frules ?annotation_rules .
215     ?annotation_metadata xyz:validation ?validation .
216     ?annotation_metadata xyz:data%5Fsource ?data_source .
217
218     #####
219     # OBSERVATION
220     #####
221     ?data fx:anySlot ?observation .
222     ?observation xyz:value ?observation_value .
223     ?observation xyz:time ?observation_time .

```

```

222     ?observation xyz:confidence ?observation_confidence .
223     ?observation xyz:duration ?observation_duration .
224     # ?observation xyz:sandbox ?observation_sandbox .
225     OPTIONAL {
226         FILTER (?object_type = "score" && ?namespace = "key_mode")
227         BIND (jams:ScoreKeyModeOccurrence AS ?occurrence_type)
228     }
229     OPTIONAL {
230         FILTER (?object_type = "audio" && ?namespace = "key_mode")
231         BIND (jams:AudioKeyModeOccurrence AS ?occurrence_type)
232     }
233     OPTIONAL {
234         FILTER (?object_type = "score" && ?namespace = "chord_roman" || ?namespace = "chord_harte" || ?namespace = "chord_poly")
#TODO change chotd -> chord_poly
235         BIND (jams:ScoreChordOccurrence AS ?occurrence_type)
236     }
237     OPTIONAL {
238         FILTER (?object_type = "audio" && ?namespace = "chord_roman" || ?namespace = "chord_harte" || ?namespace = "chord_poly")
#TODO change chotd -> chord_poly
239         BIND (jams:AudioChordOccurrence AS ?occurrence_type)
240     }
241
242     OPTIONAL {
243         FILTER (?namespace = "chord")
244         BIND (jams:RomanChord as ?chord_type)
245         BIND (chord:Chord as ?chord_equivalence)
246     }
247     OPTIONAL {
248         FILTER (?namespace = "chord_harte")
249         BIND (jams:HarteChord as ?chord_type)
250         BIND (roman:Chord as ?chord_equivalence)
251     }
252     OPTIONAL {
253         FILTER (?namespace = "chord_polychord")
254         BIND (jams:PolyChord as ?chord_type)
255         BIND (poly:Chord as ?chord_equivalence)
256     }
257
258     #####
259     # FILE METADATA
260     #####
261     ?x xyz:file%5Fmetadata ?file_meta .
262     ?file_meta xyz:title ?title .
263     ?file_meta xyz:jams%5Fversion ?jams_version .
264     ?file_meta xyz:identifiers ?ids .
265     ?file_meta xyz:release ?release .
266     ?file_meta xyz:duration ?fduration .
267     ?file_meta xyz:artist ?artist .
268
269     # PLACEHOLDER URIs
270     BIND (IRI(CONCAT(STR(chord:resource), "%2F", STR(?observation_value))) AS ?chord_uri)
271     BIND (IRI(CONCAT(STR(pon-resource:JAMSAnnotation%2F), STR(?jams_annotation_type))) AS ?annotation_uri)
272     BIND (IRI(CONCAT(STR(pon-resource:JAMSObservation%2F), STR(?observation_value))) AS ?observation_uri)
273     BIND (IRI(CONCAT(STR(pon-resource:JAMSMetricalTime%2F), STR(?annotation_duration))) AS ?metrical_time_uri)
274     BIND (IRI(CONCAT(STR(pon-resource:JAMSMetricalTime%2F), STR(?observation_time))) AS ?metrical_time_uri)
275 }
276 }

```

Listing 4.3: SPARQL CONSTRUCT query template to extract JAMS information and build the ChoCo-KG using our proposed ontology and SPARQL Anything.

External links. We link the resources in the ChoCo KG to two other large-scale datasets on the Web:

1. **MusicBrainz** [5]. We extract, from the original datasets (Section 4.1.1.2), MusicBrainz resource identifiers in the JAMS `file_metadata.identifiers.MB` field when these are available. We append them to the MusicBrainz namespace to find their MusicBrainz URIs, and make links between these URIs and the JAMS ChoCo URI where they were found, using the `skos:closeMatch` predicate. This yields 545 links.
2. **MIDI Linked Data Cloud** [11]. The ChoCo chord annotations can be useful for harmonic analyses of existing scores and symbolic music representations, e.g. MIDI. To link MIDI URIs with ChoCo URIs, we compare the string similarity the MIDI original filename and the JAMS `file_metadata` name, both typically containing the band/artist and song names, and link them through `midi:midiOf` if their similarity is $>.80$. This yields 2,411 links.

4.1.2 Reuse and Applications

The availability of a large chord dataset, providing high-quality harmonic annotations with temporal information, content metadata, and links to external resources, is of considerable interest to several research communities. In the field of MIR, chord datasets are a fundamental prerequisite for training and evaluating content-based music algorithms that can accommodate a variety of tasks – from chord recognition and cover song detection, to the evaluation of automatic composition systems. For musicology and computational music analysis, the scale and diversity of ChoCo would enable large scale cross-corpus studies across different musical periods, genres, and artists (e.g. uncovering potential influences), and the KG can also be leveraged to run complex queries entailing certain musicological properties of chords, rather than relying exclusively on their notation-specific label. Moreover, the Semantic Web community would certainly benefit from the introduction of high quality chord data that can be linked to existing Web resources and music knowledge graphs, which in turn opens up new scenarios and research opportunities for the former communities.

4.1.2.1 First experiments in Polifonia

An example of novel application at the intersection of both SW and MIR is the Semantic Music Player that the Polifonia consortium demonstrated at the 2021 “AI and Music festival” by SONAR⁶ [3]. By leveraging the semantic integration and linking of three ChoCo partitions – including pop (Isophonics), jazz (JAAH), and classical (Schubert Winterreise) music, a mobile app providing an augmented listening experience was developed on top of the resulting KG. During playback of a song, and depending on the user’s preferences and liking, the app can visualise semantic links to related music pieces, depending on controllable musical facets (e.g. harmonic and lyrics similarity) and common entities (e.g. locations, contexts of production). Whereas the harmonic similarity links are enabled by the chordal content of ChoCo, all the other connections were obtained from linking metadata information of these three partitions with MusicBrainz, Second-

⁶<https://www.starts.eu/agenda/aimusic-festival-sonar-cccb/detail/>

HandSongs⁷, Songfacts⁸, Genius⁹, and Wikidata. Overall, this application provided an example of how the ChoCo KG can be leveraged for music listening and recommendation, other than corroborating the potential of SW technologies in such domain – using ontologies to model musical content and relationships explicitly, transparently and meaningfully, as opposed to black-box AI methodologies.

Another line of research that is of particular interest to Polifonia is the creation of music similarity networks [3], and their consequent investigation through network data analysis techniques. In a music similarity network, nodes typically represent artists, composers, or music pieces (or a relevant grouping of the former), whereas edges express content-specific relationships of similarity. In the context of ChoCo, this has already lead to the design of new methods for harmonic similarity, which in turn, are fuelling the creation and the expansion of the *Harmonic Network*¹⁰ (induced from the application of these methods on a chord dataset). The computational analysis of the Harmonic Network can indeed reveal interesting insights resulting from the exploration of harmonic relationships from a global perspective, building upon the local 1-to-1 relationships on which similarity is usually defined. This includes, and it is not limited to, tracing potential influences between authors and across pieces, identifying common harmonic patterns and structures, discovering disruptive artists/pieces, as well as providing analytical support to formulate or test musicological hypotheses. For instance, an algorithmic procedure on the Harmonic Network may discover, or empirically confirm, that two authors use similar but not identical harmonic structures, even though there is no direct connection between them, but possibly through the influence of a third entity.

4.1.2.2 Applications and tasks

Given the diversity, size, and quality of the corpus, we expect ChoCo to enable novel applications in Music Technology, other than supporting the design and the evaluation of methods addressing specific tasks in both MIR and computational music analysis. Besides the aforementioned applications in music listening and recommendation, another relevant case study involves the advancement of systems for machine creativity. In the context of our work, these include automatic (or semi-automatic) composition, with particular focus on *arrangement generation* through continuation and in-painting (generating a chord progression, possibly given a melody to accompany); and *melody generation* through harmonic conditioning (generating a melody to play along with a chord progression that is provided as an harmonic template).

Not only does ChoCo support the creative capabilities of such systems – by providing a considerable amount of quality training data, but it also contributes to their automatic *evaluation*. In fact, the evaluation of music generation systems has recently attracted a growing interest in the field, due to the concerning ethical implications these tools are raising . On one hand, this involves the

⁷<https://secondhandsongs.com/>

⁸<https://www.songfacts.com>

⁹<https://genius.com/>

¹⁰<https://github.com/polifonia-project/lharp>

extraction of statistical features quantifying the degree of alignment between a generated repertoire and the training material, with respect to certain musical properties ; on the other hand, it concerns with detecting potential sources of plagiarism in generated music within and beyond the training set .

Another application domain that can potentially benefit from the Chord Corpus is that of *music pedagogy*. For example, TheoryTab¹¹ allows users to choose from a repertoire of popular songs and visualise their harmonic/melodic structure during playback – with chords encoded in both Leadsheet and Roman notations and projected in such a way as to facilitate the theoretical understanding of the song. Chordify¹² uses chord recognition systems to infer and align chord progressions from audio recordings, and provides support for practising them with guitar, piano, and ukulele. Despite their value, both the technology and the data powering these commercial tools are not openly available, thereby decreasing their overall wider use. In contrast, ChoCo provides an attractive open and linked solution, with its modular architecture enabling the semantic description of chords according to the desired level of complexity and granularity (e.g. an educational ontology for chords might provide a simpler vocabulary). As a result, this makes it more appealing and flexible for educational purposes.

In the context of MIR, the use of ChoCo as a collection, development/test set, ontology, and knowledge graph, can support a multitude of tasks. The nature of its contribution is twofold: (i) it provides an unprecedented amount of training data, which is often essential for the effectiveness of supervised methods; (ii) it contributes to the development of graph-based methodologies for music analysis that can leverage the semantic representation of chord progressions. For instance, a central research area in MIR is *music similarity*, which in turn encompasses a number of interrelated tasks, including *cover song detection* – useful for music cataloguing and to support court decisions in music plagiarism ; and content-based *music retrieval*, aiming to search scores or performances from musical repositories using either symbolic queries, singing (alias query-by-humming). Another striking example of MIR task that would clearly benefit from ChoCo is *music structure analysis* , which is concerned with the detection and labelling of structural segments related to musical form – a task that strongly relies on the use of harmonic/melodic features . Another task of interest is *music classification* or tagging , a term used to denote a family of more specific problems, including *music genre/style classification*, *mood/theme recognition*, *composer/artist identification*, and so forth. Nevertheless, as harmony can also be used by composers to create and release tension in music , ChoCo provides a compelling resource for *music emotion recognition*. In addition, considering the multimodal context of its annotations (audio and scores), it also contributes to *audio/symbolic alignment*. Finally, examples of tasks of musicological interest that would also benefit from ChoCo include *pattern mining*, *cadence detection*, and *local key identification*.

¹¹<https://www.hooktheory.com/theorytab>

¹²<https://chordify.net>

4.1.2.3 Online survey

Since ChoCo is a new resource for the SW, MIR and Musicology communities, we discuss here evidence for potential adoption. To gather such evidence, we performed an online survey in which we directly ask potential adopters 10 questions regarding their background, relevance, and interest in working with chord data. The online survey was distributed in the SW, International Society for MIR (ISMIR), and Digital Musicology mailing lists, gathering a total of $N = 28$ responses. The survey was run online using Google Forms¹³ and the results are illustrated in Figure 4.3. Except for questions 1-3 and 12, all questions ask the respondents to quantify the agreement with the statement made from 1 (absolutely disagree) to 5 (absolutely agree), being 3 a neutral response (no agree nor disagree). In the first three questions we assess the background of the respondents, finding that 28% of the participants have expertise in Semantic Web, 70% in Music Information Retrieval, and 46% in Musicology¹⁴. We also found that most participants use symbolic music data (75%) and audio music (53%), whereas a considerable portion of them use them jointly in multi-modal studies (32%). Concerning the nature of music data, most participants use structured data in CSV, JSON, etc. format (82%), unstructured data from the Web (53%), online databases (42%) and RDF data (25%). To conclude, as it emerges from Figure 4.3, we collected considerable evidence motivating the need and the potential future impact of ChoCo from different communities of music researchers and practitioners.

¹³<https://forms.gle/ndr1NoHLeDTzqaph6>

¹⁴A participant can have more than one field of expertise.

Figure 4.3: Summary of the responses of the survey on the interest on using ChoCo.

4.2 MIDI2vec: MIDI Embeddings for Music Knowledge Graph Interlinking

Predicting links to external datasets in music knowledge graphs is a challenging task. Here, we look at the task of music knowledge graph interlinking from the angle of knowledge graph link prediction. More specifically, if we consider music in symbolic form that might be missing descriptive metadata (such as author, composition year, genre, etc.), the tags expressing that missing metadata could be, in particular, resources expressed in another music knowledge graph. Therefore, in the below, we reformulate the problem of music knowledge graph interlinking as a problem of music metadata completion.

High-quality metadata is a prerequisite in many music information retrieval (MIR) tasks, like accessing symbolic music collections, music recommender systems and discovery [113]. Historically, the availability of this metadata has depended on manual human annotation labour, which is typically costly. Consequently, several systems have been proposed that automatically analyse music in order to annotate high-level features, some being abstract enough to be close to traditional metadata [69]. Most of these systems target the so-called *symbolic representation* of music: this representation explicitly describes the notes and their properties – timbre, tempo, velocity, etc. – on individual tracks for the different instruments, as opposed to the digital audio which encodes a sampled musical signal (i.e. a recording). Due to the need for high-quality annotated datasets, these systems have many real-world applications. For example, digital libraries for musicology can use them for automatically tagging metadata, lowering manual annotation costs and improving results of music information retrieval systems. In recently proposed music knowledge graphs [11], these systems could be used to complete the missing information in the graph. Another application is in machine learning for music, which needs large amounts of music data annotations that could be provided by such systems, for applications such as data programming [114] or weak supervision [115] or even music recommender systems based on similarity.

This evaluation work focuses on symbolic music in MIDI format [12], in particular in its representation through music knowledge graphs [11], due to its high availability on the Web, its high presence in the Polifonia project [87], and its popularity in tasks like music generation [74]. This popularity has also given birth to large MIDI datasets that need, besides high-quality annotations, scalable approaches producing them. Despite their natural fit as a transcription format for music, MIDI files alone have several limitations, all concerning the fact that track information (instruments, vocals, metadata) is not standardized and often only implicit [116]. One way of addressing this is to express MIDI information using RDF and ontologies [11], allowing for the re-use and standardization of missing MIDI metadata at Web scale. The Lakh MIDI dataset [116] is another important MIR benchmark used in e.g. automatic audio transcription; however, only 31,034 of its 176,581 MIDI files (17.57%) are aligned with metadata from the Million Song Dataset [117]. Reconstructing this kind of high-level metadata from symbolic musical content, automatically and at scale, is a challenging task due to the existing semantic gap between the desired metadata and low-level music descriptors [118]. One way of addressing this is by analysing the content of the symbolic notation for predicting higher-level metadata, i.e. identifying symbolic patterns in melody, harmony, rhythm, structure, etc. that are characteristic of a certain genre or composer. So far, research has mainly focused on genre [119, 71], emotion, and composer [120] clas-

sification mainly using supervised machine learning techniques. However, traditional machine learning algorithms are limited by the need to perform some feature selection in the so-called feature engineering process [121]. In order to overcome this, embedding-based methods have been proposed. Embeddings are mappings that transform the symbolic representations of discrete variables (elements that cannot be naturally ordered such as words or songs) into numeric vectors. Each dimension of an embedding vector represents a latent feature that has been automatically learned. Avoiding more expensive representations such as the one-hot encoding, embedding vectors are useful at reducing the dimensionality of the input data of neural networks, a typical choice to address a learning task such as automatic classification. Such embedding-based methods have been successfully applied to textual [122] and graph data [89] and notably also on MIDI data for the task of automated music generation through Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) [123, 124] and self-learning techniques such as Variational Autoencoders (VAE) [74]. Graph embeddings have become a widely used and effective way to represent graph information in a way neural networks can easily process it [125].

Here, we describe and repurpose MIDI2vec [25], a method designed within Polifonia in collaboration with other researchers and institutions for representing MIDI data as vector-space embeddings for automated metadata classification, link prediction, and knowledge graph interlinking. First, we express MIDI files as graphs, assigning unique identifiers to specific characteristics and their values such as tempo, time signature, programs (instruments), and notes. Therefore, two MIDI files will be connected in the graph if they share the same resources (e.g. same instruments, chords, tempo, etc.). Second, we use graph embedding techniques – and in particular the *node2vec* algorithm [89] – to traverse these MIDI graphs with random walks, and represent the information of the traversed paths as numeric vectors. We assume that these traversals will encode not only MIDI information that is relevant for a given song, but also additional neighbouring information of similar songs that can be relevant for metadata classification. In other words, we assume the distributional semantics hypothesis [126] over MIDI features: notes or groups of notes used in similar contexts will tend to have similar meanings, and in particular, will be associated with similar features, even for high-level metadata such as genre, composer or instrument.

4.2.1 Graph Embeddings

Graph embeddings are the result of the transposition of word embedding techniques – notably word2vec [122] and GloVe [127] – to networks. According to [128], a graph can be defined as a set $G = (V, E)$, where V is a set of vertices (or nodes) and E is the set of edges, represented as pairs of directly connected vertices. Graph embedding algorithms produce a mathematical representation – consisting of a set of vectors – of the content of the graph, which is much more compact than other kinds of representation (e.g. adjacency matrix) and consequently easier and faster to process with Machine Learning. The effectiveness of these techniques makes them very popular in different applications, from classification to recommendation, with an interesting number of algorithms developed for their computation. An extensive survey has been realised by [129].

In 2014, Perozzi et al. published Deep Walk [130]. The core idea of this work consists in the

use of random walks in the graph in order to generate sequences of nodes. The number and the length of link paths between two nodes impact the probability of those two nodes being selected together in the random walk. In other words, the more two nodes share connections¹⁵ in the graph and the fewer edges compose those connections, the more those nodes will appear together in several walks. According to the intuition of the authors, we can deal with nodes in sequences as they are words in sentences, so it is possible to apply word embedding models, and by extension, the distributional semantics hypothesis, to those sequences. The transition probabilities between nodes replace the one between words in the embedding computation. The result is a vector space in which distances in the graph are kept.

DeepWalk has been extended by **node2vec** [89], with the inclusion of two parameters P and Q , which rule on the generation of random walks. In particular, the parameter P impacts the probability that the random walk immediately revisits the previous node. The parameter Q controls the probability that the random walk moves towards increasingly further away nodes, enabling the discovery of peripheral parts of the graph. In other words, higher values of P promote random walks that explore a local neighbourhood around the starting node, while high values of Q encourage walks that cover wider areas of the graph. *Node2vec* can be also applied to weighted graphs, in which the weight of an edge affects the probability that it participates in the walk.

Other notable embedding-based techniques have been proposed for representing nodes in a graph, such as *rdf2vec* [125], *entity2vec* [131], *graph2vec* [132] for graph embeddings, and many others¹⁶.

4.2.2 Learning MIDI Embeddings

The MIDI format does not present a graph structure, but it consists of a time-based linear succession of events, called *MIDI messages*, detailed in the specification [12]. Some examples are *Note On* and *Note Off* for representing played notes, *Program Change* for setting the instrument, and *MTC Quarter Frame Message* for specifying the playing speed according to the MIDI Time Code (MTC) protocol. This last information impacts the duration of the interval between two Song Position Pointers (SPP), which identify the time at which the message occurs, expressed in MIDI beats from the beginning of the song (commonly referred to as *ticks*). Some of the MIDI messages are referred to a specific channel (a single device emitting music, in other words a single instrument), while others can apply to the whole MIDI. Because of this structure, we first need to convert the MIDI into a graph, on which embeddings can be computed afterwards.

¹⁵Two nodes are connected if exists one or more paths of edges between them, of which the two edges represent respectively the first and the last node involved. A connection can consist of a single edge; in this case, we can speak about directly connected nodes.

¹⁶A regularly updated list of software for embedding generation is available at <https://github.com/MaxwellRebo/awesome-2vec>

4.2.2.1 MIDI to Graph

We propose a preliminary conversion of a MIDI file into a graph which mimics that of the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [11], albeit with some differences to include relevant note information closer in the graph topology. Specifically, the MIDI Linked Data Cloud uses the ontology shown in Figure 4.4, which reuses elements of the Musical Feature PON module (e.g. `mf:Note`) (see D2.1 [3]), especially regarding the representation of low-level music resources (e.g. `mid:Note`). This ontology, and its usage in e.g. SPARQL CONSTRUCT queries in SPARQL Anything [133], makes the automated construction of MIDI KGs straightforward (see Chapter 3 and Section 4.1.1). This representation is useful to produce MIDI knowledge graphs that are faithful representations of the MIDI standard and mimic existing representations in widespread music programming libraries, e.g. `music21`¹⁷. However, such representations can be cumbersome from an embeddings perspective, as they tend to keep relevant musical aspects (e.g. groups of notes, their length, pitch, program, tempo, etc.) too far apart in the graph. This has the inherent limitation that standard random walks will hardly traverse them together and, therefore, relevant proximity information will not be encoded in the embeddings.

To address this, we transform this first MIDI ontological model to another one that groups resources in a way that groups of related notes, and their properties, are kept together. As shown in Figure 4.5, a *MIDI node* (the circle) represents the MIDI file and will be connected to nodes representing different parts of the MIDI content (i.e. tempo, programs, time signature, notes). A MIDI node can be linked to one or more nodes for each type.

In the context of graph embeddings computation, the practice is to take into account only connections between entities, that are nodes represented by identifiers. Literal values (text, numbers, etc.) are normally ignored [125] or some shrewdness is applied such as the use of contiguity windows [134]. In fact, literals can increase uncontrollably the number of nodes, in particular in presence of continuous values or entity-specific textual annotation. The effect is a very sparse graph¹⁸, causing an exponential increment of the computation time and poor performance [135]. In our case, the crucial information represented as continuous data (e.g. the tempo) can not be excluded from the embeddings. We opted for partitioning the continuous values in ranges, in order to insert their information in the graph, while limiting at the same time the number of nodes. We provide some details for each type of node in the following.

Tempo, computed in *bpm* (beats per minute). This value is computed from the MIDI tempo field (in microseconds per beat), according to the formula:

$$Tempo_{bpm} = 60000000 / Tempo_{midi} \quad (4.1)$$

The continuous values are then discretised in partitions, each one representing a range of 10 bpm. Example: `tempo-11` represents the range of values 110 ± 5 bpm.

Programs, representing the timbre of the channels, among the 128 different standard pro-

¹⁷See <http://web.mit.edu/music21/>

¹⁸A graph is considered *dense* or *sparse* if its number of edges is close or far, respectively, to the number of all potential edges connecting each pair of vertices [128].

Figure 4.4: Excerpt of the MIDI ontology used to represent MIDI files in the MIDI Linked Data Cloud. The low-level music resources (e.g. `midi:Note`) are linked to resources in the Musical Feature PON module (e.g. `mf:Note`).

Figure 4.5: Schema of the graph generated from MIDI. The + indicates edges representing connections of type many-to-many. The colours represent different groups of nodes: MIDI M (blue), Content C (orange) among which Notes N have a round shape, and Attributes A (grey).

grams¹⁹. Example: `program-0` is the Acoustic Grand Piano.

Time signature is the measure of how many beats are contained in each measure. It is represented as the concatenation of numerator and denominator. Example: $\frac{4}{4}$ is represented as `ts-4/4`.

¹⁹The full list of MIDI programs is available at <https://jazz-soft.net/demo/GeneralMidi.html>

Figure 4.6: MIDI graph example, showing possible connections between MIDI #1, #2, and #3.

Notes, representing the pitches in the MIDI. The information about duration and co-occurrence of notes (e.g. in a chord) are not directly represented in the MIDI file. The duration is extracted by comparing successive *NoteOn* and *NoteOff* events sharing the same pitch and located on the same channel. Co-occurring notes can be detected by comparing the same category of events among all channels, selecting the ones with overlapping *Song Position Pointers* (SPP). To include this information in the graph while limiting the number of nodes and edges, we extract all groups of notes starting (i.e. with a *NoteOn* message) at the same SPP. A tolerance of 10ms is applied for considering two notes simultaneous, to overcome eventual small differences due to MIDI recording. Each group is connected to:

- the maximum duration of the notes in the group, discretised in classes of 100ms. Example: the id `duration-3` represents the range 300 ± 50 ms.
- their average velocity. Example: `velocity-1`.
- all the pitches, identified by their standard MIDI numbers. Example: `note-57` is A-3.

Each group has an identifier that is deterministically computed from its content using a hash function. These groups are then linked to the relative MIDI node. This ensures that two identical groups of notes have the same identifier, linked to all MIDI nodes in which this group appears without any further effort.

MIDI2vec does not encode any information concerning time, in particular about sequences of notes occurring in the same channel. This information is undoubtedly relevant and crucial in music representation. Nevertheless, we decide to not include the time dimension in this experiment for two main reasons. First, the inclusion of order and sequentiality in a graph representation is not very common and few works addressed this topic so far [136, 137]. Second, this would require some choices, among them the number of consecutive notes to be grouped and the opportunity of representing pauses in the graph or not. For this reason, we decided to consider the

encoding of subsequent notes for future work.

The connections between nodes are mostly of type *many-to-many*, so that two involved nodes are potentially part of other instances of the same connection. Taking as an example the connections between Tempo and MIDI types, this means that a specific Tempo node may be linked to different MIDI – pieces sharing the same tempo – and a specific MIDI may be linked to different tempos – representing a tempo change in the track. Some connections can be instead of type *one-to-many*: this is the case of the Group of Notes, linked to exactly one Duration which is, in turn, connected to several Group of Notes. Two MIDI nodes are never directly connected. Tempo, programs, and time signature might change within a file; we register all of them as equal nodes.

Formally, we realise a graph $G = (V, E)$, where $V = M \cup C \cup A$. M corresponds to the set of MIDI files. C corresponds to the first level of MIDI content, including tempo, programs, time signature, and the set $N \in C$ referring to groups of notes. A corresponds to the attributes of groups of notes, in particular to duration, velocity, and pitch. The edges in $E = E_M \cup E_N$ can belong to two types. An edge $(m, c) \in E_M$ indicates that the MIDI $m \in M$ has $c \in C$ as part of its content; this category also includes edges (m, n) linking a MIDI m to a note group $n \in N \in C$. While $(n, a) \in E_N$ indicates that the group of notes $n \in N$ has the attribute $a \in A$.

In Figure 4.6, an excerpt of an example graph is provided, in particular showing the connections between MIDI files through complete note groups, single notes, duration, etc. In this kind of graph, two MIDI tracks sharing multiple chords (or other elements) will have more probability to appear in the same random walk. This representation aims to track at the same time the presence of specific chords and of quick and long notes, which can respectively characterise a more virtuous or lyrical composition.

The graph is saved in the edgelist format, which includes all couples of connected nodes. In the edgelist, each line of text represent an edge and contains the identifiers of the two involved nodes separated by blank spaces. In practice, the MIDI files are read and messages are sequentially converted and appended to the edgelist. This edgelist is the output of this first conversion and feeds the second part of the approach, described in the next section. Such obtained graph contains only information extracted from the MIDI content, not including any kind of external metadata.

4.2.2.2 Graph to Vectors

Embeddings are computed on the output graph of the previous process with the *node2vec* algorithm. As more extensively written in Section 4.2.1, the algorithm simulates random walks on the graph and computes the transition probabilities between nodes, which are mapped into the vector space. In other words, two MIDI files sharing programs, tempos, note groups are more likely to be part of the same random walk and consequently are more likely to be close in the computed embedding space.

In practice, each node in the graph is selected as the starting node for a random walk, occupying its first slot. The second slot will be occupied by one of the nodes directly linked to the first node, according to the probability function. Iteratively, every slot of the random walk will be occupied

by one of the neighbours of the previous one. The number of walks to be produced for each node and their length are given parameters. These walks are then processed by *word2vec* as they are sentences. The graph configuration, with few properties and densely connected nodes, make us prefer an approach based on random walks – representing similarities between nodes’ neighbourhoods – rather than those based on latent spaces of relations (e.g. TransE) [138].

Following this procedure, a 100-dimensions embedding vector is computed for each node (vertex) of the input graph. Each dimension of the vector cannot be attributed to a specific feature of the described item – for example, the tempo – but it rather represents latent features learned by the embedding algorithm. We apply a post-processing step in order to keep only the vectors $m \in M$ representing the MIDI files, excluding consequently all the nodes that refer to MIDI messages and attributes.

Such obtained vectors can be then used in input to algorithms, in tasks such as classification, clustering, and others. In the experiment which will be detailed in the following section, we will use such generated vectors in input to a neural network for classification. In particular, all vectors used in our experiment have been computed using the following configuration of *node2vec*: walk length = 10, number of walks = 40, window size = 5, number of iterations = 5, $p = 0.1$, and $q=0.1$. We opted for a relatively short walk length, balanced by a higher number of walks: this was due to the highly connected graph structure, in which longer walks would easily cover quite distant parts of the graph. This is consistent with a notion of musical locality, in which musically similar, recurring events typically appear close together. The rest of the parameters are similar to the default ones. We also published as open-source the library for producing MIDI embeddings at <https://git.io/midi2vec>.

4.2.3 Evaluation

We evaluate this strategy in relation to the general goal of general link prediction (i.e. interlinking) of MIDI datasets. For this, we use the Lakh MIDI dataset, a subset of all MIDI files included in the music knowledge graph of the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [11], included in Polifonia [139, 87].

We perform an experiment that relies on a common procedure: MIDI embeddings are generated on the dataset using MIDI2vec. The, a Feed-Forward Neural Network receives the MIDI embeddings as input (100 dimensions) in batches of size 32. The network is detailed in Figure 4.7. The choice of a Feed-Forward NN is due to the fact that that we do not capture the MIDI content as a temporal series – which would be necessary for working with e.g. CNN or Transformers – but as a list of connections. This also serves the purpose of investigating whether the graph topology (i.e. similarity of close musical patterns) is informative for finding links without taking into account the sequential character of music (a question that we leave for future work; albeit multiple existing models already point to a positive answer [140, 74]).

The set of labels used for training and testing is in accordance to that of Lakh, but it could arbitrarily be changed by e.g. resources belonging to external knowledge graphs. However, it is worth reminding the reader that those labels have not been used in the embedding task, and consequently, they are not directly included in the embedding information. The neural network

consists of 3 dense layers. The hidden layers count 100 neurons each and use $ReLU^{20}$ as activation function. The output layer uses a sigmoid²¹ as activation function and has a number of neurons equal to the dimension of the vocabulary of labels, which is represented with one-hot encoding. We performed 10-fold cross-validation²² for training the neural network and we provide as final score the average of the accuracy²³ computed on every fold.

Figure 4.7: Scheme of the neural network.

Currently, the library deals with the unpitched notes in MIDI Channel 10 (reserved to percussion by specification) as they have a pitch. When we ignore Channel 10 and use only programs representing pitched instruments²⁴, we empirically observe that the average scores remain substantially unchanged (less than 1% of difference), while the standard deviation is around 2% higher. For this reason, we report here only the performances obtained considering note events from all channels.

These experiments are available as notebooks at <https://git.io/midi-embs>, which contains also the plots included in this paper in high resolution. Furthermore, all edgelist and learned embeddings for each dataset are also published for supporting research reproducibility at <https://zenodo.org/record/5082300>.

²⁰A rectified linear unit (ReLU) is a classic activation function in Deep Learning networks, which return 0 when the input is negative or the input value itself when it is positive. ReLU is widely used because of its simplicity and its empirically demonstrated fast convergence.

²¹The sigmoid function transforms the input x according to the formula:

$$h_{\theta}(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\theta^T x}}$$

It exists between 0 and 1, so it is widely used when probabilities are requested in output. Its step curve shape gives it a behaviour similar to the Heaviside step, but derivable for any input.

²²In 10-fold cross-validation, the dataset is split into 10 groups, choosing in sequence each of them as test set (10%) and the remaining 9 as training set (90%).

²³The definition of *accuracy* is “the closeness of agreement between a test result and the accepted reference value”, i.e. the true value (ISO 5725-1).

²⁴Musical instruments can be classified as *pitched*, producing recognisable notes in the musical scale (e.g. the piano), or *unpitched*, producing sounds of indefinite pitch (e.g. the cymbals).

4.2.4 Link Prediction Experiment

The Lakh MIDI Dataset (LMD)²⁵ is one of the biggest collections of MIDI which have been realised for research purposes [117]; it is included in the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [11]. An `LMD-matched` subset contains 31,034²⁶ MIDI aligned to entries of the Million Song Dataset, providing a set of metadata about the tracks, the albums and the artists. Figure 4.8 shows a breakdown of the notes, instruments, tempo and time signature found in MIDI of the Lakh dataset.

Figure 4.8: From left to right and top to bottom, notes, instruments, tempo and time signature of the MIDI in the Lakh dataset (31,036 files). The average note is B3 (we have omitted all drum events in channel 10); the most frequent instruments (peaks) are the acoustic grand piano, string ensemble 1, and acoustic guitar (steel). The average tempo is 213.15 bpm, estimated with [141]. The most common time signature is 4/4; 2/4 is also relatively frequent.

We extracted from `LMD-matched` two kinds of tags, coming respectively from MusicBrainz²⁷ and The Echo Nest²⁸. The former group is a mix of terms that may refer to genres – i.e. *classic*

²⁵Lakh MIDI Dataset: <https://colinraffel.com/projects/lmd/>

²⁶The LMD website declares that `LMD-matched` includes 45,129 MIDI. However, only 31,034 of them have metadata within an HDF5 file.

²⁷MusicBrainz: <https://musicbrainz.org/>

²⁸The Echo Nest: <http://the.echonest.com/>

pop – or to nationalities – *British* – while the latter group is more homogeneous in representing genres. Both kinds of tags refer more to the artist rather than to the exact track.

The size of the dataset allows to further filter the data to extract a balanced dataset. In particular, we select all distinct classes which are represented by at least 50 instances. For each of these classes, we randomly select 50 instances. Table 4.2 shows the accuracy for the predictions, measured through 10-fold cross-validation, together with the number of classes (distinct tags) against which we run the classification. In addition, in the table are reported the accuracy scores obtained by an SVM classifier built on top of jSymbolic. The comparison of these results reveals that latent features can largely boost the performance in tag classification, at least in cases where the number of items and especially classes is high, with evident benefit in real-world scenarios like automatic tag prediction.

feature	n. items	n. classes	midi2vec	jSymbolic
MusicBrainz	2400	48	39.7% (2.8%)	3.7% (1.4%)
EchoNest	6800	136	32.5% (1.9%)	1.4% (0.4%)

Table 4.2: For each kind of tag feature, the table reports the number of items, the number of distinct classes, the average (and standard deviation) accuracy score for midi2vec and jSymbolic.

The confusion matrices are shown in Figure 4.9. Among the most wrongly predicted MusicBrainz classes, we find a strong presence of nationality tags (*British, Italian, UK*, etc.). The consistent number of classes make complicate to detect patterns in the confusion matrix, in which the best values are however concentrated in the diagonal of corrected predictions. To overcome this issue, we report in Table 4.3 the most frequent wrong predictions. For MusicBrainz tags, the list includes loosely defined genres (*easy listening, ccm*), one evident error (line 6.), together with couples of tags that can be considered similar or overlapping (1., 3., 7.). Looking at EchoNest tags, all pairings are meaningful, involving similar or related genres. This data gives us more confidence that the neural network is learning music-relevant features, which are well represented through graph embeddings.

tag	ground truth	predicted	%
MusicBrainz	1. ballad	folk rock	12
	2. blues-rock	ccm	12
	3. classic rock	british invasion	12
	4. cool jazz	ccm	10
	5. easy listening	classic rock	12
	6. flamenco	british invasion	12
	7. folk rock	ballad	10
EchoNest	8. orchestra	requiem	10
	9. progressive trance	hard trance	10
	10. ragtime	jazz	10
	11. requiem	orchestra	10
	12. techno	tech house	10

Table 4.3: Most frequent prediction errors for tag classification, with the percentage of cases over the total of the class

(a) MusicBrainz Tag prediction

(b) The Echo Nest Tag prediction

Figure 4.9: Confusion matrices of midi2vec predictions for the Lakh dataset.

5 FAIR Protocol

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

1. ChoCo Knowledge Graph (ChoCo-KG) dataset¹
2. MIDI2vec algorithm²
3. MIDI2vec edgelists and learned embeddings³

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [142]. In particular, via GitHub the both the ChoCo dataset and the MIDI2vec algorithm's source code have a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Additionally, all MIDI2vec experiments are available as notebooks at <https://git.io/midi-embs>. The data produced by the MIDI2vec algorithm (edgelists and learned embeddings) is available as a Zenodo deposit at <https://zenodo.org/record/5082300>. Once ChoCo is published through an ongoing paper in progress, we will deposit the dataset in Zenodo and publish its stable URL in GitHub. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook⁴ [2], the ChoCo dataset and MIDI2vec algorithm are integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. The storage of all resources on Github guarantees their persistence beyond the project. Additionally, we plan on adding to ChoCo and MIDI2vec fine-grained provenance descriptions, using standards for interoperable provenance representations, such as PROV [143], to the transformation processes we apply to ChoCo source datasets, and the representations of MIDI files. This is especially relevant to the issue of data authority, since the original data both approaches rely on were made available by other persons and institutions outside Polifonia.

Being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The resources created by the ChoCo dataset are themselves released as an RDF Knowledge Graph, making such resources uniquely identifiable to a fine-grained level, findable through the Web Portal, accessible through e.g. SPARQL queries, interoperable via the aforementioned vocabularies, and reusable via open source licenses. Because of this very nature, the ChoCo dataset will be also straightforwardly integrated in the Web Portal.

Finally, MIDI2vec is released with a CC-BY 4.0 licence that allows all resources to be copied and redistributed in any medium or format. The material may also be remixed, transformed, and

¹[GitHubURLisupcominguponthedataset'srelease.](#)

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/midi2vec>

³<https://zenodo.org/record/5082300>

⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

build upon for any purpose, even commercially. We are investigating the complexities of licensing ChoCo content, as the dataset relies on the various licenses of the original partitions; for now we are including these in the aforementioned provenance representations.

6 Conclusions

In this report, we have described the first Polifonia project efforts for building, and interlinking, music knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage. Departing from the state of the art in collaborative knowledge graph engineering methodologies, existing datasets in the pilots, and methods for knowledge graph construction and interlinking, we have proposed ideas that address core challenges in building and interlinking music knowledge graphs: (a) the selection of an adequate methodology for building knowledge graphs in the Polifonia pilots; (b) a framework for the construction of music knowledge graphs that integrates music content and context; and (c) techniques that leverage the graph-like structure of such Polifonia music knowledge graphs to discover and generate missing links at scale with high accuracy. We have demonstrated the preliminary results of these frameworks and techniques in two successful use cases: (1) ChoCo-KG, a knowledge graph of 30M+ RDF triples and 3K+ links of chord annotations; and (2) MIDI2vec, a technique that uses graph embeddings over symbolic music knowledge graphs to predict missing links with high accuracy. A first evaluation shows that a sample of researchers in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and Semantic Web acknowledge the need of, and would be interested in, using ChoCo-KG for a variety of tasks; and that MIDI2vec can scale to finding links in very large music knowledge graphs by outperforming state of the art methods by an order of magnitude.

In the future we will extend this work in various ways. First, and foremost, we will continue to work close to the Polifonia pilots in order to support them in generating knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage from all their sources, appropriately integrating their construction pipelines within Musilar and Cornucopia. Second, we will continue to extend SPARQL Anything [20] with more converters (MIDI, MEI, MusicXML, ABC, etc.) and Facade-X and query templates, as demanded by the stories, personas, and competency questions of the pilots. Third, we will improve the Similarity ontology module and include similarity semantics that mirror the links and relationships uncovered by links between the various pilot knowledge graphs. Fourth, we will publish and find specific early adopters for the ChoCo-KG; the ACCESS pilot could be a good candidate due to their harmony studies among deaf people. Finally, we plan to extend MIDI2vec [25] to generate embeddings over any of the music knowledge graphs of the project, pushing the boundaries of its capacity to find links between different music knowledge graphs. This could have enormous potential to feed larger music models, inspired in current language models [144], for generating music at scale [145, 146]. Additionally, we plan to enable wider access to the interlinked Knowledge Graphs of Polifonia via Knowledge Graph APIs [147, 148, 149, 150].

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